

**PREDICTING JOB SATISFACTION AMONG NONPROFIT HEALTH AND
HUMAN SERVICE EMPLOYEES: THE ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL
IDENTIFICATION AND ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE**

by

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Abstract

Guided by social exchange theory, this quantitative study examined how organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural) predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. A cross-sectional approach was used, and data were collected via SurveyMonkey Audience from 186 eligible full-time nonprofit health and human service employees. Multiple linear regression analysis was performed to examine the relationships among the variables and evaluate the relative strength of each predictor. Results indicated that the overall regression model significantly predicted job satisfaction, demonstrating meaningful explanatory power. Organizational identification, informational justice, and interpersonal justice were significant predictors, while distributive and procedural justice were not significant when analyzed simultaneously. Informational justice emerged as the strongest predictor, suggesting that perceptions of transparent and adequate communication are critical to employees' job satisfaction. These findings support social exchange theory by showing that employees who perceive fair communication, respectful interpersonal treatment, and a strong psychological connection to their organization report higher job satisfaction.

Dedication

This dissertation is first dedicated to my younger self, who once questioned whether an achievement such as this was possible. This work stands as a reminder that perseverance, growth, and belief in one's potential can lead to accomplishments that once felt out of reach. The journey to this point has been shaped by challenges, self-doubt, and determination, and this milestone represents not only academic achievement but personal growth and resilience. I also dedicate this work to my husband and children, whose patience, understanding, and unwavering support made this journey possible. Your willingness to accept missed activities, late nights, and the many sacrifices required to complete this program gave me the time and space to pursue this goal. A special dedication is extended to my mother, whose constant support and quiet acts of care, especially in easing the pressure of daily responsibilities, provided comfort and stability throughout this process.

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CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

Nonprofit health and human service organizations play a critical role in supporting the well-being of individuals and communities across the United States (United States Department of Health and Human Services, n.d.). Despite the essential nature of this work, organizations in this sector face persistent workforce challenges, including high emotional demands, limited resources, and turnover. These conditions highlight the importance of understanding the organizational factors that influence employee satisfaction and workforce stability. Among the factors that may shape employee attitudes are perceptions of organizational justice and organizational identification. Accordingly, this study examined whether organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

This chapter introduces the study by presenting the background of the problem, the problem statement, the research questions, the rationale for the study, and its significance. Additionally, the chapter identifies the gap in existing literature that the study aims to address and provides an overview of the research methodology used to examine the relationships among the study variables. Key terms are defined to ensure clarity and consistency, and the assumptions and limitations related to the research design are outlined. The study is based on social exchange theory, which offers a theoretical framework for understanding how perceptions of organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice may influence job satisfaction.

Background of the Study

Employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations play a critical role in meeting the acute and long-term needs of individuals and communities across the United States. These organizations operate for public or social benefit rather than profit generation and often depend on a stable, committed workforce to sustain service delivery (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, n.d.). However, employees in these settings frequently work under conditions characterized by emotional labor, resource constraints, and elevated risk of burnout, all of which may influence workplace attitudes and overall job satisfaction (Costakis et al., 2021; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). As workplace expectations continue to evolve, employees increasingly expect fairness, respect, transparency, and alignment between personal and organizational values (Lian et al., 2022; Mascarenhas et al., 2022). These conditions make it especially important to understand the organizational factors that shape job satisfaction within this workforce.

A central concern in Industrial/Organizational psychology is how employee experiences within the workplace influence attitudes and outcomes. Prior research has documented meaningful relationships among organizational identification, organizational justice, and job satisfaction (Hong et al., 2024; Vásquez-Trespalcios et al., 2023). Organizational identification reflects the degree to which employees experience a psychological sense of connection and alignment with their organization (Lian et al., 2022), whereas organizational justice reflects employees' perceptions of fairness in workplace outcomes, procedures, communication, and interpersonal treatment (Colquitt, 2001). Research conducted in for-profit and healthcare settings suggests that organizational justice is positively associated with both job satisfaction and organizational identification (Avanzi et al., 2021; Jilili & Aini, 2023; Zagenczyk et al., 2021).

However, less is known about how these variables operate collectively within nonprofit health and human service organizations, despite the unique demands of this work context.

Social exchange theory provides a meaningful framework for examining these relationships. Social exchange theory proposes that employee attitudes develop through reciprocal exchanges between employees and their organizations, with perceptions of fairness, support, and treatment shaping the quality of those exchanges (Homans, 1958). When employees perceive fair procedures, equitable outcomes, respectful treatment, and transparent communication, they may be more likely to respond with stronger organizational identification and greater job satisfaction. Conversely, perceived inequities may weaken these relational bonds and contribute to dissatisfaction (Vaamonde et al., 2018). Within social exchange theory, fair treatment may strengthen employees' psychological connection to the organization and promote more favorable evaluations of their work experience.

Although existing literature highlights the importance of fairness, identification, and satisfaction for employees' well-being and retention (Çakiroğlu, 2022; Lian et al., 2022; Mascarenhas et al., 2022), important gaps remain in understanding how these constructs interact within nonprofit health and human service organizations. Much of the existing research has examined these variables independently or in for-profit contexts, leaving limited insight into how they interact in nonprofit environments, where resource constraints, mission-driven work, and high emotional demands may shape employee experiences differently. As a result, there is a need for research that simultaneously examines perceptions of organizational justice, organizational identification, and employee job satisfaction. Exploring these relationships may provide insights that improve organizational practices, inform human resource strategies, and support workforce sustainability in this vital sector.

Problem Statement

The problem addressed in this study is the decline in job satisfaction among employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations and the limited understanding of how organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice are associated with job satisfaction in this workforce. Employees in these settings often work under emotionally demanding conditions and within resource-constrained environments, which may heighten the importance of workplace fairness, belonging, and alignment of organizational values (Costakis et al., 2021; Mascarenhas et al., 2022; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). Research has shown that perceptions of unfair treatment are associated with lower job satisfaction, weaker organizational identification, and increased intention to quit (Çakiroğlu, 2022; Vásquez-Trespacios et al., 2023). Declining job satisfaction may therefore contribute to workforce instability, higher turnover, and reduced morale within nonprofit health and human service organizations.

This problem carries important organizational consequences for nonprofit health and human service organizations. When job satisfaction is low, organizations may experience increased turnover, reduced morale, and diminished workforce stability. High turnover can strain remaining staff, disrupt service continuity, and compromise outcomes for individuals and communities. In mission-driven nonprofit environments, where organizations often operate with limited financial and human resources, workforce instability can significantly hinder effectiveness (Costakis et al., 2021). Because nonprofit health and human services rely heavily on committed employees to deliver essential services, understanding the organizational conditions associated with job satisfaction is particularly important. Examining factors that contribute to employee satisfaction may therefore help nonprofit health and human service organizations strengthen workforce stability and maintain the continuity of services they provide.

What remains poorly understood is how much organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) together predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Although previous research has explored some of these relationships, much of the existing literature has studied these constructs separately or within different organizational settings, leaving little research that examines them together within this specific population (Malhotra et al., 2022; Vásquez-Trespalcacios et al., 2023). Gaining a clearer understanding of how these variables interact could provide valuable insights into the organizational processes that influence employee attitudes and workplace experiences in nonprofit health and human service environments. Therefore, this study examined whether organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice significantly predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed to examine whether organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

RQ1: To what extent does the overall model of organizational identification, distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations?

RQ2: Which variables (organizational identification, distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) significantly predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations?

RQ3: Which variable is the strongest predictor of job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations?

Study Rationale

Quantitative research is designed to generalize findings beyond the immediate sample; therefore, this study intentionally addresses both the specific problem experienced by employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations and the broader issue of how the four dimensions of organizational justice and organizational identification contribute to job satisfaction across workplaces. These research questions provide a multilevel understanding of the multiple linear regression model. RQ1 assesses the overall power of the model by evaluating the impact of the five predictors (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) on job satisfaction, treated as a single model. This tests whether job satisfaction can be meaningfully explained by the combined set of predictors. It focuses on overall model fit and determines whether it is worthwhile to interpret the individual predictors in later questions. RQ2 assesses the significance of individual variables by examining each predictor's unique contribution while controlling for others. This helps identify which predictors are statistically significant after accounting for variable overlap and distinguishes important predictors from those that do not meaningfully contribute once other factors are considered. It also provides theoretical insight into which forms of distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice, along with organizational identification, are most relevant for predicting job satisfaction. RQ3 compares predictors to determine their relative

influence. This identifies the most influential predictor within the model and helps prioritize variables for practical application, policy, or organizational intervention. It also adds depth beyond statistical significance by addressing the magnitude of effect.

Building on this framework, it is important to recognize the unique context faced by the target population. The specific population, full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations, faces unique pressures related to chronic stress, emotional labor, and burnout (Costakis et al., 2021; Vásquez-Trespalcios et al., 2023). These organizations represent a significant segment of the U.S. workforce and play a critical societal role by meeting the acute and long-term needs of communities (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2024). However, research addressing how the four dimensions of organizational justice, combined with organizational identification, jointly predict job satisfaction in this sector remains extremely limited (Knapp et al., 2019). By focusing on this under-examined workforce, the study is designed to fill a meaningful gap in scholarly knowledge regarding the predictors of job satisfaction among nonprofit human service employees, especially related to the dimensions of organizational justice, which research shows are key contributors to dissatisfaction, turnover intentions, and diminished organizational identification when perceived as low (Vásquez-Trespalcios et al., 2023).

Beyond addressing the needs of this specific workforce, the study's design also supports generalizability. It contributes to the Industrial/Organizational psychology literature by examining an expanded set of organizational justice variables related to job satisfaction and organizational identification. Prior studies have predominantly focused on limited dimensions of justice or single predictors (Hong et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024) and have not examined these constructs together within a single predictive model. Additionally, as organizations across

sectors continue adapting to the post–COVID-19 landscape marked by heightened employee expectations for fairness, transparency, and belonging (Lian et al., 2022; Mascarenhas et al., 2022; West, 2022), this study provides timely insight into how these factors collectively influence satisfaction. By grounding the study in social exchange theory, the findings can guide organizations broadly in strengthening justice practices, enhancing identification, and improving job satisfaction. Thus, while the study directly benefits nonprofit health and human service workers by addressing a critical gap in understanding predictors of their job satisfaction, it also extends generalizable evidence that can inform organizational strategy and employee well-being across diverse workplaces.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it provides practical, scholarly, and theoretical insights into job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Practically, the findings can help nonprofit leaders, human resource professionals, and organizational decision-makers better understand workplace conditions that influence employee satisfaction. By highlighting the relative impact of organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice, the study may guide strategies to enhance perceptions of fairness, strengthen employees' connection to the organization, and support employee retention and workforce stability. These insights can assist nonprofit health and human service organizations in developing management practices and workplace policies that promote positive employee experiences and supportive work environments. Ultimately, improving employee satisfaction can help organizations maintain a stable workforce and continue delivering essential services to their communities.

The study is also important for the broader nonprofit and community context. High turnover and low job satisfaction in nonprofit organizations can disrupt service delivery, increase organizational strain, and weaken continuity of care for the individuals and communities these organizations serve (Vincent & Marmo, 2018). Workforce instability may also force organizations to dedicate significant time and resources to recruiting, training, and onboarding new employees, thereby diverting attention from mission-related activities. Because nonprofit health and human service organizations often serve vulnerable or underserved populations (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, n.d.), staffing disruptions may impact the consistency and quality of services provided. By identifying organizational factors linked to job satisfaction, the findings may contribute to broader discussions about nonprofit workforce support, service sustainability, and community well-being.

From a scholarly perspective, the study contributes to the Industrial/Organizational psychology literature by examining organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice together in relation to job satisfaction within a population that has received comparatively limited attention (Knapp et al., 2019). Much of the existing research has focused on single predictors, individual dimensions of justice, or organizational contexts outside the nonprofit health and human service sector (Hong et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024). As a result, there is limited empirical evidence regarding how these constructs collectively relate to job satisfaction among nonprofit health and human service employees. By examining these variables simultaneously within a single predictive model, the study extends the literature and provides a more comprehensive understanding of the factors associated with employee job satisfaction in a mission-driven organizational environment. The findings may therefore offer additional insight

into how perceptions of fairness and organizational connection interact to influence employee attitudes.

This research is also theoretically significant because it applies social exchange theory to examine job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Social exchange theory suggests that employees assess the fairness and quality of their exchanges with the organization, and these evaluations influence work attitudes and behaviors, including organizational identification and job satisfaction (Homans, 1958). When employees perceive fair treatment and supportive organizational relationships, they are more likely to develop stronger organizational identification and more positive attitudes toward their work. Applying this framework enables the study to explore how perceptions of fairness and organizational connection work together to shape employee satisfaction. By examining these relationships in nonprofit organizations characterized by high emotional labor, service-oriented missions, and limited resources, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of how social exchange processes function within mission-driven work environments.

Identified Gap

Although organizational identification and organizational justice are widely studied as predictors of job satisfaction (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019; Yuan et al., 2016), existing research falls short in several ways, leaving important questions unanswered, especially for employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Most studies only look at limited combinations of the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural) or focus on single predictors of job satisfaction, which creates inconsistencies in the literature and overlooks how these four dimensions interact with organizational identification to impact job satisfaction (Hong et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024). As a

result, the combined effect of organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice has received limited attention within nonprofit human service organizations. Much of the current research offers only a partial understanding of how perceptions of fairness and employees' psychological connection to their organization influence job satisfaction together. Therefore, there is a clear need for studies that examine these factors simultaneously within a single predictive model for full-time employees working in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

Addressing this gap is important because nonprofit health and human service employees often work in environments characterized by high emotional labor, increased burnout risk, and ongoing workforce instability, all of which may influence how employees interpret fairness and develop connections to their organizations (Costakis et al., 2021; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). These conditions may affect the extent to which employees' perceptions of organizational justice and identification with their organization contribute to overall job satisfaction. Despite the critical role nonprofit health and human service organizations play in supporting individuals and communities, empirical research examining the combined impact of these variables within this workforce remains limited. Investigating these relationships may therefore provide a more comprehensive understanding of the organizational factors associated with job satisfaction in this sector. By addressing this gap, the present study contributes to the literature by examining organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice as predictors of job satisfaction among full-time employees working in nonprofit health and human service organizations. In doing so, the study offers insights that may support the development of fairer organizational practices and more sustainable workforce strategies within mission-driven organizations.

Overview of the Methodology

This study used a quantitative, predictive correlational design to examine whether organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. A quantitative design is appropriate because the study aims to evaluate theoretical relationships among measurable variables and determine the extent to which specific predictors influence a defined outcome (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Predictive correlational designs are appropriate for evaluating theoretical relationships and determining the strength and direction of associations among variables without manipulating the research setting. This approach is consistent with the positivist perspective that knowledge is most efficiently developed through objective measurement and statistical analysis (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This methodological approach is also appropriate for the discipline of Industrial/Organizational psychology, where quantitative research frequently informs evidence-based organizational decision-making and evaluates work-related attitudes, perceptions of fairness, and job satisfaction.

The selection of this design aligns directly with the stated research problem: employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations experience reduced job satisfaction when perceptions of organizational justice are low, which may diminish organizational identification and negatively affect retention (Vásquez-Trespacios et al., 2023). Quantitative methodology enables the empirical determination of whether perceptions of fairness and organizational identification significantly predict job satisfaction and identify which justice dimensions contribute most strongly. This study used validated survey instruments, including Mael and Ashforth's Organizational Identification Scale, Colquitt's (2001) Organizational Justice Scale,

and the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Weiss et al., 1999), to measure the independent and dependent variables. Using standardized instruments supports reliability, validity, and comparability with prior research in organizational justice and job satisfaction (Judge et al., 2017; van Dijke et al., 2018). Because the population of interest consists of full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations, online survey administration provides an efficient means of reaching geographically dispersed participants while yielding sufficient statistical power to conduct multiple regression analyses.

This methodology is grounded in the theoretical foundation guiding the study. Social exchange theory posits that employees evaluate the fairness, reciprocity, and quality of workplace interactions when forming attitudes such as organizational identification and job satisfaction (Homans, 1958). Quantitative correlational designs are commonly used to test exchange-based predictions because they allow researchers to examine how perceived inputs, such as justice, communication, and interpersonal treatment, relate to employee outcomes, including satisfaction and identification. The approach is further supported by the existing literature, which calls for research that simultaneously examines multiple justice dimensions and organizational identification as predictors of job satisfaction, particularly among nonprofit health and human service employees, a population underrepresented in current studies (Knapp et al., 2019; Malhotra et al., 2022). Although quantitative research may overlook deeper contextual meanings behind participants' experiences, it is the most appropriate and discipline-aligned method for addressing the stated research questions, which require identifying predictor variables and assessing the strength of their relationships with job satisfaction. Multiple regression analysis allows for determining both overall predictive capacity and the unique contribution of each justice dimension in explaining job satisfaction levels (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Overall, the quantitative, predictive, correlational methodology provides a rigorous and appropriate approach to addressing the research problem, filling the identified gap, and contributing evidence-based insights to Industrial/Organizational psychology and nonprofit workforce practices.

Definitions of Terms

Distributive justice. Distributive justice refers to employees' perceptions of fairness regarding the outcomes or allocations resulting from organizational decisions (Colquitt, 2001). Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale (Colquitt, 2001) measured distributive justice.

Full-time. Full-time status indicates an employee who works at least 30 hours per week. Full-time status can also apply to employees who work 130 hours per month (Internal Revenue Service, 2023).

Health and human services. Health and human services refer to programs and services designed to promote the health, safety, and well-being of individuals and communities (United States Department of Health and Human Services, n.d.).

Informational justice. This dimension of justice focuses on the extent to which information is communicated openly, honestly, and fairly among organizational members (Colquitt, 2001). Informational justice was measured through Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale (Colquitt, 2001).

Interpersonal justice. The perceived quality of interpersonal interaction in the workplace, which helps define one's well-being (Colquitt, 2001). Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale measured interpersonal justice (Colquitt, 2001).

Job satisfaction. Job satisfaction refers to an individual's personal evaluation of their feelings about their work, which may vary along a spectrum from dissatisfaction to satisfaction

(Judge et al., 2017). Job satisfaction was operationalized using the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire, which captures employees' evaluations of both intrinsic and extrinsic aspects of their work (Weiss et al., 1999).

Nonprofit. Nonprofit organizations operate for collective, public, or social benefit and do not distribute profits to owners or shareholders (The Office of the New York State Attorney General, 2024).

Organizational identification. Organizational identification represents a psychological association through which employees perceive a sense of connection and alignment with their organization (Lian et al., 2022). Organizational identification was measured using Mael and Ashforth's six-item scale (Jiang et al., 2024).

Organizational justice. Organizational justice refers to employees' perceptions of workplace fairness and encompasses four dimensions: distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice (Colquitt, 2001). Organizational justice was measured by Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale (Colquitt, 2001).

Procedural justice. Procedural justice concerns how employees evaluate the fairness of organizational processes, including whether procedures are applied consistently to people and remain stable over time (van Dijke et al., 2018). Procedural justice was measured by Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale (Colquitt, 2001).

Social exchange theory. In social exchange theory, the reciprocal interactions between employees and employers influence the development and strength of their dyadic relationship (Homans, 1958).

Assumptions and Limitations

This section outlines the key assumptions and limitations that guide and constrain the present study. All research is grounded in assumptions regarding methodology, theory, and subject matter, which must be acknowledged to clarify the foundation on which the study is built. Likewise, identifying the study's limitations is essential for understanding the boundaries of its findings, the potential influences on data interpretation, and the extent to which results may be generalized. Together, these assumptions and limitations provide important context for evaluating the validity, reliability, and scope of the research on organizational identification, organizational justice, and job satisfaction among nonprofit health and human service employees.

Assumptions

The assumptions guiding this investigation derive from three core sources: the methodological expectations of quantitative research, the theoretical grounding in social exchange theory, and the subject-matter context of nonprofit health and human service work. Methodologically, quantitative research assumes that constructs such as organizational identification, organizational justice, and job satisfaction can be objectively measured through validated instruments and that participants will respond accurately and honestly (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Theoretically, social exchange theory assumes that employee attitudes emerge from ongoing reciprocal exchanges between individuals and their organizations (Homans, 1958). Additionally, given the unique demands of nonprofit health and human service work, this study assumes that employees possess adequate experience, understanding, and insight to meaningfully report on their perceptions of fairness, alignment, and job satisfaction (Costakis et al., 2021;

Vincent & Marmo, 2018). These assumptions underpin the study's methodology and interpretations.

Theoretical Assumptions

This study is grounded in social exchange theory, which includes several theoretical assumptions relevant to understanding organizational identification, perceptions of organizational justice, and job satisfaction. Social exchange theory posits that relationships between employees and their organizations are grounded in reciprocal interactions, in which individuals evaluate the costs and benefits of their workplace experiences to assess the quality of the exchange (Homans, 1958). A core assumption is that employees are actors who rely on relational exchange and judge fairness, support, and treatment based on their perceptions of how the organization fulfills its obligations (Gong et al., 2025). When employees perceive fair procedures, equitable resource distribution, respectful interpersonal interactions, and transparent communication, they are likely to feel that the organization has upheld its end of the exchange, increasing their identification with the organization and enhancing job satisfaction. Social exchange theory also assumes that positive exchanges accumulate over time and contribute to trust, commitment, and stronger organizational alignment, while negative exchanges, such as perceptions of injustice, diminish these attitudes and may foster dissatisfaction or withdrawal behaviors (Montañez-Juan et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2024). Thus, the theoretical assumption guiding this study is that perceptions of organizational justice and feelings of identification emerge in response to ongoing exchanges between employees and their organizations, ultimately shaping job satisfaction among nonprofit health and human service workers.

Subject Matter Assumptions

Several subject-matter assumptions guided this study and pertain specifically to nonprofit health and human service workers who participated in the survey. It is assumed that nonprofit health and human service workers experience organizational dynamics similar to those documented in prior studies of human services and healthcare employees, including exposure to high emotional demands, risk of burnout, and sensitivity to fairness-related practices (Costakis et al., 2021; Vásquez-Trespacios et al., 2023). Additionally, this study assumes that participants understand the terminology and survey items related to justice perceptions, identification, and satisfaction, as these measures have been validated across diverse organizational and human service populations (Colquitt, 2001; Judge et al., 2017). Finally, it is assumed that the participants' responses reflect their authentic workplace experiences and attitudes, given the voluntary and confidential nature of the survey. These subject-matter assumptions ensure that the data collected meaningfully represent employees' lived organizational experiences in nonprofit health and human service settings.

Limitations

A primary limitation of this study is its reliance on self-report survey data, which introduces the potential for response bias. Although validated instruments such as Colquitt's (2001) organizational justice scale, Mael and Ashforth's organizational identification scale (Jiang et al., 2024), and the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Weiss et al., 1999) have been widely used across organizational research, they still rely on participants' subjective perceptions. Participants may unintentionally distort their responses due to social desirability bias, misunderstanding of items, or emotional states shaped by the demands of nonprofit health and human services work. Nonprofit employees often experience considerable emotional strain

(Costakis et al., 2021), which may influence how they interpret fairness, belonging, and job satisfaction when responding. Thus, while the instruments are psychometrically sound, the inherent subjectivity of self-report data remains a limitation.

Another limitation arises from the quantitative predictive correlational design. While this methodology is appropriate for examining relationships among variables and assessing the extent to which organizational identification and dimensions of organizational justice predict job satisfaction, it does not permit causal inference (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Unmeasured variables, such as burnout, leadership style, workload, compensation systems, or organizational culture, may also influence job satisfaction and perceptions of justice among nonprofit health and human service employees. Research indicates that employees can experience high organizational identification even when job satisfaction is low (Hong et al., 2024; Yuan et al., 2016), demonstrating that additional contextual factors likely shape these outcomes. Because correlational studies cannot account for all possible confounding influences, the predictive relationships identified in this study should be interpreted with caution.

The study's sampling frame presents another limitation. By focusing exclusively on full-time employees in U.S. nonprofit health and human service organizations, the generalizability of the findings is restricted. Nonprofit health and human service organizations are unique in their mission-driven structure, resource constraints, and emotionally demanding environments (Costakis et al., 2021; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). These characteristics differ from those in for-profit workplaces, general healthcare organizations, or government agencies. For example, nonprofit health and human service workers are known to experience elevated turnover due to stress, emotional exhaustion, and identity misalignment (Loi et al., 2014; Vincent & Marmo,

2018). As a result, the findings may not extend to part-time workers, newly hired employees, other nonprofit sectors, or the for-profit workforce.

Another limitation is the assumption that nonprofit health and human service organizations operate similarly in structuring procedures, distributing resources, and communicating information. In practice, these organizations vary widely in size, leadership style, funding stability, and service modality. Such differences may influence employees' perceptions of distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice (van Dijke et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2024). Organizational identification may also manifest differently across organizations, depending on their missions, cultures, and employee support structures (Lian et al., 2022; Tekingündüz et al., 2020). These variations may lead to responses that the study's design cannot fully capture.

The cross-sectional nature of the research also presents a limitation. Cross-sectional data capture a single point in time, making it impossible to determine whether perceptions of justice, identification, or job satisfaction change as workplace conditions evolve. Nonprofit health and human service workers face ongoing challenges, including chronic stress and burnout, particularly in the years following the COVID-19 pandemic (Mascarenhas et al., 2022; Vásquez-Trespalacios et al., 2023; West, 2022). These dynamic conditions may influence employees' perceptions in ways that are not observable in cross-sectional designs. Longitudinal designs would provide a stronger basis for identifying how perceptions and attitudes develop or shift over time, but fall outside the scope of the current methodology.

Organization of the Remainder of the Study

Chapter 1 introduced the background, problem, and purpose of this study, which explores the relationships among organizational identification, distributive, informational, interpersonal,

and procedural justice, and job satisfaction among employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. The chapter established the study's significance to Industrial/Organizational psychology, outlined the theoretical framework of social exchange theory, and identified gaps in the literature regarding the influence of organizational justice and identification on job satisfaction in this population. Additionally, the research questions and objectives were presented, and the rationale for employing a quantitative, predictive correlational methodology was outlined.

In Chapter 2, the literature review provides a comprehensive analysis of the scholarly literature on organizational identification, the four dimensions of organizational justice, and job satisfaction. This chapter synthesizes previous research, identifies trends, findings, and gaps in the existing literature, and focuses on the health and human services sector. The theoretical and practical significance of social exchange theory is further examined to frame the proposed study's hypotheses and research questions.

Methodology is discussed in Chapter 3, which outlines the research design, population, sampling strategy, and data collection procedures for the study. This chapter details the quantitative, predictive, correlational approach, the survey instruments used to measure organizational identification, distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice, and job satisfaction, and the planned statistical analyses, including multiple regression. Ethical considerations, instrument reliability and validity, and potential limitations of the study are also discussed.

Data analysis is presented in Chapter 4. This chapter uses descriptive and inferential statistics to address the research questions and evaluate the relationships among organizational identification, the four dimensions of organizational justice, and job satisfaction. Findings are

presented in tables, figures, and narrative summaries to clearly communicate patterns, trends, and statistical significance. In Chapter 5, a synthesis of the findings is included, discussing their implications for theory, practice, and future research. This chapter connects the results to the literature reviewed in Chapter 2, offers recommendations for nonprofit health and human service organizations to enhance employee job satisfaction, and highlights the study's limitations. Finally, conclusions are drawn, summarizing the research's contributions to the field of Industrial/Organizational psychology and to the broader understanding of organizational justice and identification in nonprofit work settings.

CHAPTER 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study examined job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations, with particular attention to the roles of organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural). Chapter 2 presents the theoretical framework, grounded in social exchange theory, and provides a comprehensive review of relevant literature. The literature search was guided by carefully selected keywords aligned with the predictor and outcome variables. The chapter synthesizes existing research, identifies gaps and inconsistencies in the current body of knowledge, and evaluates the methodological approaches used in prior studies.

Methods of Searching

The literature search for this study was conducted primarily through Capella University's library databases, including Business Source Complete, EBSCOhost, PsycARTICLES, PsycINFO, and ProQuest, with additional searches performed using Google Scholar. Priority was given to locating research in Industrial/Organizational psychology that directly addressed the study's variables. The search was limited to peer-reviewed scholarly publications from the past seven years to capture the most current developments in research related to organizational identification, organizational justice, and job satisfaction. Foundational and seminal works were included when necessary to provide theoretical grounding and historical context. Keywords included *industrial and organizational psychology*, *job satisfaction*, *justice*, *organizational justice*, *distributive justice*, *informational justice*, *interpersonal justice*, *procedural justice*, *perception*, and *satisfaction*.

Background of the Study

The four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) and organizational identification have been widely studied as key constructs influencing employees' work-related outcomes, including job satisfaction. Organizational justice refers to employees' perceptions of workplace fairness and encompasses four dimensions: distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice (Colquitt, 2001). Organizational identification is defined as a psychological bond that connects employees to their organization (Lian et al., 2022). Together, perceptions of justice and identification within the organization provide an important framework for understanding employees' evaluations of their work environment and overall job satisfaction. In examining these relationships, demographic characteristics, such as sex, are routinely collected to describe sample composition and to provide contextual information for interpreting findings. Although sex is not examined as a predictor or explanatory variable in the study, reporting participant sex contributes to transparent characterization of the sample and supports consideration of the generalizability of the results.

Theoretical Framework for the Current Study

Social exchange theory (SET) provides a foundational lens for understanding the relationships that shape employee behaviors within organizations (Homans, 1958). Drawing on the work of Homans (1958), SET posits that social interactions are guided by the expectation of mutual benefit, in which individuals evaluate the balance between the resources they contribute and the rewards they receive (Farid et al., 2019). In organizational settings, this framework helps explain how perceptions of fairness, support, and recognition influence employees' levels of commitment, identification, and job satisfaction. By applying SET to the current study, the

examination of employee responses to organizational justice and organizational identification is grounded in a well-established model of human interaction and reciprocity (Farid et al., 2019; Koçak & Kerse, 2022). This theoretical foundation provides a basis for assessing how employees form judgments about their work environment and how these judgments affect their overall job satisfaction (Desrumaux et al., 2023).

Social Exchange Theory

George Homans' (1958) work on social exchange theory serves as the framework for this study. Homans proposed that social behavior can be understood as a relationship between two entities, shaped through a process of cost-benefit analysis, which molds a person's perception of that exchange within that specific relationship (Roch et al., 2024; Straatmann et al., 2020). Later, Blau expanded SET to emphasize the development of long-term social relationships grounded in trust and mutual benefit, rather than solely in economic transactions (Roch et al., 2024). These exchanges develop into norms that define expectations for future transactions (Gong et al., 2025), which is why SET is one of the most widely used frameworks for examining workplace relationships (Roch et al., 2024).

At its core, SET assumes that social relationships operate through a series of exchanges in which people evaluate the benefits they receive relative to the contributions they make (Farid et al., 2019). These exchanges may involve tangible resources, such as compensation or job security, or intangible resources such as respect, recognition, fairness, and support. A key principle of SET is reciprocity (Farid et al., 2019; Straatmann et al., 2020). When employees perceive favorable treatment from the organization, they feel obligated to reciprocate through positive attitudes and behaviors, such as higher satisfaction, commitment, or performance (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022). Conversely, perceptions of inequity or unfair treatment may lead to

reduced motivation, lower trust, or withdrawal behaviors (Vaamonde et al., 2018). Thus, SET provides a systematic explanation of how employees interpret organizational actions and how those interpretations influence workplace outcomes.

SET has been widely applied in organizational research to explain employee reactions to fairness (Desrumaux et al., 2023; Farid et al., 2019), leadership behavior, organizational support, and identification (Koçak & Kerse, 2022). Studies have shown that when employees perceive fair treatment, transparent communication, and respectful interactions, they are more likely to experience higher levels of job satisfaction and engagement (Dar & Rahman, 2019). Research grounded in SET consistently demonstrates that organizational justice, whether distributive, procedural, informational, or interpersonal, functions as a form of social exchange that shapes employee attitudes (Farid et al., 2019). This theoretical foundation has been instrumental in understanding how employees develop trust in their organizations (Koçak & Kerse, 2022) and why perceived fairness influences their willingness to contribute positively (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022).

Although SET is influential and widely used, it is not without limitations. Critics argue that the theory can oversimplify complex human motivations by focusing primarily on cost-benefit relations (Koçak & Kerse, 2022). Others note that SET may not fully account for cultural or individual differences in perceptions of reciprocity or fairness (Straatmann et al., 2020). Additionally, some scholars contend that the theory assumes mutually beneficial exchanges, even though organizational settings may involve unequal power dynamics that constrain employees' ability to reciprocate (Desrumaux et al., 2023; Farid et al., 2019; Vaamonde et al., 2018). Despite these limitations, SET remains a robust and versatile framework for studying workplace relationships.

Social exchange theory is directly relevant to this study because it provides a conceptual foundation for understanding how employees interpret and respond to organizational justice. When employees perceive that their organization treats them fairly, through equitable decision-making processes, respectful communication, and consistent application of policies, they are likely to reciprocate with increased job satisfaction (Vaamonde et al., 2018). Conversely, perceptions of injustice may disrupt the exchange relationship and reduce satisfaction (Vaamonde et al., 2018). SET therefore offers a coherent lens for examining how perceptions of organizational justice and identification shape employee attitudes, like job satisfaction, within the health and human services sector.

Review of the Literature

This literature review explores employees' perceptions of organizational justice and organizational identification within the workplace and examines how these factors relate to job satisfaction. Specifically, it considers the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, procedural, informational, and interpersonal) and their influence on employees' attitudes and behaviors. The review also addresses the concept of organizational identification, highlighting how employees' sense of belonging and alignment with organizational values interact with perceptions of fairness to shape overall job satisfaction. By integrating findings from multiple studies, this review aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms through which organizational justice and identification impact employees' workplace experiences. Following a review of the existing literature, the discussion synthesizes key findings, identifies gaps in current research, and critically evaluates the methodologies employed in prior studies. This approach not only highlights areas requiring further empirical investigation but also

establishes a foundation for understanding how organizational justice and identification jointly contribute to employee well-being, engagement, and satisfaction.

Organizational Identification

Organizational identification, as defined by Mael and Ashforth (1992), is a state in which individuals internalize their membership in the organization to the point that they associate themselves with its outcomes, regarding organizational successes and failures as personally significant. Avanzi et al. (2023) further elaborate on the point that organizational identification is a specific form of social identification. According to these definitions, organizational identification is a psychological state in which employees define themselves in terms of the organization (Avanzi et al., 2023; De Giorgio et al., 2023). From a social identity perspective, when employees perceive themselves as part of a particular organization, they begin to internalize its values and goals and view themselves as fundamentally and psychologically connected to other members. When this sense of membership becomes psychologically meaningful, employees are more likely to act in ways that favor the organization (Caputo et al., 2024), for example, by demonstrating higher engagement, greater cooperation, and increased willingness to go beyond their formal job requirements (Dechawatanapaisal, 2018). Because organizational identification captures the strength of individuals' connection to their organization, it serves as a valuable framework for understanding and predicting a wide range of workplace attitudes and behaviors. Employees who identify strongly with their organization are, in turn, more likely to exhibit extra-role performance (Lian et al., 2022), more substantial commitment, and higher job satisfaction (Afrahi et al., 2025; Dechawatanapaisal, 2018).

Organizational identification is closely connected to Social Identity Theory (SIT) (Lin & Liu, 2019), even if SIT does not serve as the primary theoretical framework for this dissertation.

SIT helps illuminate why employees come to define themselves in terms of their organizational membership, emphasizing that individuals derive part of their self-concept from the groups to which they belong. When employees identify with an organization, they internalize its norms and values, linking their personal identity to the workplace's collective identity (Lin & Liu, 2019; Zagenczyk et al., 2021). However, while SIT provides valuable insight into the cognitive and social processes underlying identification, the broader understanding of identity within organizations extends beyond this single theoretical lens. Identity theory, which focuses on the internalization of role expectations and the alignment of the self with meaningful social positions, contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of how identification functions within organizational behavior (Lin & Liu, 2019; Malhotra et al., 2022). Within this broader context, identity becomes intertwined with key organizational dynamics, including belongingness, motivation, and cultural alignment (Lin & Liu, 2019). A strong sense of identity supports a sense of belonging by helping employees feel accepted and integrated into the organizational community (Lin & Liu, 2019; O'Connor & Crowley-Henry, 2019). It enhances motivation by aligning personal meaning with organizational goals, thereby encouraging employees to act in ways consistent with their identities (Kundi et al., 2023).

Identity orientation is commonly described as having three forms: personal, relational, and collective, with each linked to a distinct pattern of social exchange (Mael & Ashforth, 1992). Individuals who emphasize a personal identity orientation typically approach interactions through a short-term, self-interested, transactional mindset. In contrast, a relational identity orientation involves exchanges based on mutual reciprocity with specific partners, in which obligations are tied to direct interpersonal relationships (Mael & Ashforth, 1992). A collective identity orientation, however, is associated with more generalized forms of exchange in which

employees act with the intention of benefiting the organization rather than particular individuals (Koçak & Kerse, 2022; Mael & Ashforth, 1992). At this level, traditional notions of reciprocity no longer fully capture how exchange relationships operate. Instead, social identity becomes the central mechanism driving behavior, as employees act in ways that reflect a shared sense of membership and commitment to the collective (Lin & Liu, 2019; Tekingunduz et al., 2020).

Behavioral identification represents a key dimension of organizational identification, capturing the extent to which employees translate their sense of belonging and shared identity into concrete actions that support organizational interests (Wikhamn et al., 2021). While cognitive and affective identification reflect how employees see themselves in relation to the organization and how they feel about that relationship (Jiang et al., 2024), behavioral identification is demonstrated through the choices employees make and the behaviors they enact in their daily work (Lin & Liu, 2019; Wikhamn et al., 2021). Employees who strongly identify with their organization tend to align their actions with their perceptions of the organization's goals, values, and priorities, often going beyond formal role requirements (Vásquez-Trespalcacios et al., 2023; Yuan et al., 2016). This alignment may manifest as discretionary effort, proactive problem-solving, or voluntary engagement in activities that promote the organization's well-being, even when such actions are not explicitly rewarded. Behavioral identification thus becomes a powerful expression of agency on behalf of the organization, as employees act not only out of obligation or compliance but because they see organizational success as intertwined with their own sense of self (Lin & Liu, 2019; Mael & Ashforth, 1992). In this way, behavioral identification serves as a mechanism by which internalized identity translates into meaningful contributions that support organizational functioning, cohesion, and long-term effectiveness.

Organizational identification develops through multiple antecedents, including organizational, leadership (Lorenz, 2025), individual, and job-related factors that influence the degree to which employees internalize their organizational membership (Mascarenhas et al., 2022). Organizational factors such as a clear, coherent culture, value congruence, and perceived organizational prestige play a central role in creating an environment in which employees feel proud to belong and view the organization as aligned with their own standards (Avanzi et al., 2023). Leadership factors further reinforce this process, particularly when leaders behave ethically, communicate transparently, and demonstrate fairness in decision-making (Mascarenhas et al., 2022). Such behaviors signal respect and trustworthiness, fostering a climate in which employees feel valued and are more likely to identify with the organization (Mascarenhas et al., 2022). Individual factors, including personal values, personality traits, and prior experiences, also influence identification by shaping how employees interpret organizational practices and whether they resonate with their sense of self (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022). Job-related factors, such as autonomy, meaningful work, and growth opportunities, strengthen identification by providing daily experiences that reinforce the organization's support for employee well-being and competence (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022). Across these domains, perceptions of organizational justice function as a crucial integrative mechanism (Greco et al., 2019; Mascarenhas et al., 2022). When employees perceive fairness in procedures, interactions, and outcomes, they are more likely to develop trust in the organization and view it as legitimate, thereby deepening identification. Conversely, unfair treatment can undermine these antecedents, discouraging employees from identifying with the organization (Greco et al., 2019). In this way, organizational justice not only shapes the impact of specific antecedents but also serves as a

foundational condition that enables employees to translate positive organizational, leadership, individual, and job-related cues into meaningful organizational identification.

Organizational Justice

Organizational justice has been defined in numerous ways across the scholarly literature, reflecting its central role in shaping the quality of the employee–organization relationship. Early definitions framed organizational justice as employees’ evaluations of the fairness of the outcomes they receive, emphasizing proportionality between contributions and rewards (Sheeraz et al., 2020). Over time, the definition has expanded, with researchers describing organizational justice as employees’ perceptions of fairness in both outcomes and the processes used to determine them, while others have highlighted interpersonal treatment and communication as essential components of perceived fairness (Liao et al., 2024; Straatmann et al., 2020). Building on this work, Colquitt (2001) provides one of the most widely cited definitions, describing organizational justice as the extent to which employees perceive fairness in decision outcomes, communication they receive from organizational authorities, the quality of interpersonal treatment, and the procedures used to reach those outcomes. Colquitt (2001) further categorizes justice into four dimensions, which include distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural, highlighting the multifaceted nature of fairness in the workplace. Despite these variations, a common thread across definitions is that organizational justice captures how employees interpret and evaluate fairness in their work environment.

These perceptions of fairness within organizational justice serve as powerful psychological signals indicating whether the organization is trustworthy, legitimate, and respectful of its members (Kang & Sung, 2019). Therefore, organizational justice is crucial in shaping employee attitudes and influencing satisfaction, commitment, and trust (Kang & Sung,

2019; Roch et al., 2019). It also significantly impacts behavior, directing the degree to which employees participate in productive actions such as cooperation, organizational citizenship behaviors, and ethical conduct (Haynie et al., 2019; Sheeraz et al., 2020). Conversely, the absence of fairness can lead to withdrawn effort, resistance to change, or counterproductive behaviors (Çakiroğlu, 2020; Vaamonde et al., 2018). On a broader organizational level, perceptions of justice help foster a respectful environment, boost morale, strengthen social cohesion, and enhance the effectiveness of organizational systems and decision-making processes (Sarfraz et al., 2018). Thus, organizational justice is more than an abstract idea; it is a fundamental element that influences how employees think, feel, and act within their workplaces.

Organizational justice is closely linked to a range of employee attitudes and behaviors, particularly job satisfaction and organizational identification (Desrumaux et al., 2023; Zagenczyk et al., 2021). Employees' perceptions of fairness, whether in outcomes, processes, interpersonal treatment, or the quality of information they receive, are key determinants of how valued and respected they feel within the organization (Kung et al., 2024; Malla & Malla, 2024). When employees perceive high levels of organizational justice, they are more likely to experience job satisfaction (Yuan et al., 2016), reflecting positive evaluations of their work, environment, and relationship with the organization (Vásquez-Trespalcacios et al., 2023). Fair treatment reinforces the psychological contract between the employee and employer, promoting trust, support, and reciprocity that enhance overall job satisfaction (Cropanzano et al., 2022), with most of these feelings stemming from the supervisor-employee dyad (Mushonga, 2023). Similarly, organizational justice fosters organizational identification by strengthening employees' sense of belonging and alignment with the organization's values and goals (Lin & Liu, 2019). When individuals perceive that they are treated fairly and respectfully, they are more likely to

internalize the organization's successes and values as their own, thereby enhancing commitment and motivating behaviors that extend beyond formal role requirements (Vásquez-Trespacios et al., 2023). Conversely, perceptions of injustice can erode both satisfaction and identification, leading to disengagement, reduced commitment, and potentially counterproductive behaviors (Vaamonde et al., 2018). In this way, organizational justice functions as a foundational mechanism linking fair treatment to employees' emotional attachment, alignment of self-concept with the organization (Farid et al., 2019), and broader attitudes and behaviors that contribute to organizational effectiveness (Shehadeh, 2023).

Distributive Justice

Distributive justice refers to employees' perceptions of the fairness of outcome distributions within an organization, such as pay, promotions, rewards, workload, or recognition (Xu et al., 2024). Unlike procedural justice, which emphasizes the fairness of decision-making processes (Kang & Sung, 2019), distributive justice focuses on the equity of outcomes (Xu et al., 2024). Employees evaluate whether the outcomes they receive are proportionate to their inputs, including effort, skills, experience, and contributions (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019). The perception of fairness in outcome allocation is critical because employees' assessments of whether they are being treated equitably can strongly influence their satisfaction, motivation, and overall attitudes toward the organization (Shehadeh, 2023).

Equity theory provides a foundational lens for understanding distributive justice, emphasizing that employees are motivated not only by what they receive but also by how their rewards compare to those of others (Roch et al., 2024). When employees perceive that their inputs are matched by appropriate outcomes relative to peers, they experience a sense of fairness, which can enhance motivation, commitment, and engagement (Xu et al., 2024). Conversely,

perceptions of under-reward or over-reward relative to colleagues may trigger feelings of inequity, leading to dissatisfaction, reduced effort, or even counterproductive behaviors (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019). This comparison process underscores the importance of perceived deservedness; employees are more likely to view outcomes as fair when they are aligned with contributions, performance, or effort (Xu et al., 2024). In this sense, distributive justice is not merely a matter of equal treatment, but of equitable treatment, with outcomes that are proportionate to individual contributions and contextual expectations (Kang & Sung, 2019).

Importantly, distributive justice recognizes that unequal outcomes can be acceptable and even desirable when they are perceived as justified by relevant performance criteria (Roch et al., 2019). For example, employees may consider pay differentials, promotions, or bonus allocations fair when higher rewards are clearly linked to higher levels of performance, skill, or responsibility (Roch et al., 2019). This perspective highlights that fairness is relative rather than absolute, and that organizational members can accept differential treatment when it reflects meaningful distinctions in contributions (Roch et al., 2019). Such perceptions of justified inequality can reinforce motivation and encourage high performance, as employees understand that effort and achievement will be appropriately rewarded (Pan et al., 2018; Roch et al., 2019). Conversely, when unequal outcomes are perceived as arbitrary, biased, or unrelated to performance, they can undermine trust, satisfaction (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019), and engagement (Kang & Sung, 2019), illustrating the delicate balance organizations must achieve in allocating resources and recognition.

Overall, distributive justice is a critical dimension of organizational justice, providing insight into how employees evaluate the allocation of rewards, recognition, and responsibilities (Xu et al., 2024). By linking organizational justice to equity theory and emphasizing the role of

deservedness, distributive justice offers a structured framework for understanding the conditions under which employees accept or resist differential treatment (Roch et al., 2019). Organizations that effectively manage distributive justice, ensuring that outcomes are proportionate to contributions and clearly justified, can enhance motivation (Xu et al., 2024), strengthen commitment (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019), and foster a culture of fairness, which ultimately supports both individual and organizational performance.

Informational Justice

Informational justice refers to employees' perceptions of the fairness of information provided by the organization, particularly regarding the adequacy, clarity, honesty, and justification of communication (Lane & Aplin-Houtz, 2023). While distributive and procedural justice focus on outcomes and processes (Rahman, 2024), informational justice emphasizes the content and quality of the messages employees receive from leaders and organizational authorities (Lane & Aplin-Houtz, 2023). Employees assess whether explanations for decisions, policies, or outcomes are transparent, truthful, and complete, and whether they provide meaningful insight into the reasons for those decisions (Hughes et al., 2024). High levels of informational justice occur when organizations communicate openly, provide clear rationales for decisions, and ensure that employees are fully informed about matters that affect them, fostering trust and understanding (Pan et al., 2018). Conversely, when communication is vague, misleading, or incomplete, employees are likely to perceive the organization as secretive or manipulative, thereby eroding trust, engagement, and commitment (Hughes et al., 2024).

The adequacy and clarity of communication are central to informational justice (Hughes et al., 2024; Pan et al., 2018). Adequate communication ensures that employees receive all relevant information necessary to understand organizational decisions, changes, and

expectations, reducing uncertainty and confusion. Clarity ensures that this information is presented in a way that is comprehensible, unambiguous, and consistent across all levels of the organization. Honesty in communication strengthens employees' perceptions of the organization's integrity, signaling that leaders are credible and trustworthy (Kurdoglu, 2020). Justification, meanwhile, provides the reasoning behind decisions, helping employees understand not only what has been decided but also why it was necessary or appropriate. Together, these elements of informational justice create a communication environment in which employees feel informed, respected, and fairly treated (Lane & Aplin-Houtz, 2023).

Informational justice becomes particularly critical during periods of organizational change or when delivering negative news (Hughes et al., 2024). During restructuring, layoffs, or performance-related decisions, employees are often highly sensitive to the quality and transparency of information. When organizations communicate honestly and provide clear justifications for difficult decisions, employees are more likely to accept outcomes, even when they are personally unfavorable (Hughes et al., 2024; Liang & Ma, 2021). Conversely, inadequate or misleading communication during times of change can exacerbate uncertainty, generate rumors, increase anxiety, and reduce trust in management (Hughes et al., 2024). Research has shown that employees who perceive high informational justice are more likely to maintain positive attitudes, cooperate with change initiatives, and engage in behaviors that support the organization, even under challenging circumstances (Kurdoglu, 2020). This highlights the central role of communication fairness in shaping employee perceptions, promoting organizational stability, and preventing negative or disruptive events from irreparably damaging the psychological contract between employees and the organization.

Informational justice is an important dimension of organizational justice, focusing on the quality, clarity, and transparency of workplace communication. By ensuring that employees receive adequate explanations, honest information, and clear justifications for decisions, organizations can foster trust, reduce uncertainty, and promote engagement (Hughes et al., 2024). Its importance is particularly valuable in situations involving organizational change or the communication of negative news, where perceptions of informational justice can determine whether employees accept and support difficult decisions or respond with resistance and disengagement (Hughes et al., 2024; Kurdoglu, 2020). In this way, informational justice serves as a vital mechanism for maintaining fairness, strengthening relationships between employees and the organization, and supporting overall organizational effectiveness.

Interpersonal Justice

Interpersonal justice refers to employees' perceptions of the fairness of the treatment they receive from supervisors, managers, and other organizational authorities, with a focus on respect, dignity, and propriety in interpersonal interactions (Molines et al., 2025). While distributive justice concerns outcomes (Rahman, 2024) and procedural justice encompasses decision-making processes (Gong et al., 2025), interpersonal justice emphasizes how employees are treated on a personal level (Molines et al., 2025). Employees evaluate whether they are treated courteously, politely, and sensitively, and whether managers show consideration for their rights and feelings. Research shows that employees are highly sensitive to these interpersonal cues, as they directly affect perceptions of respect, organizational support, and relational quality in the workplace (Singh et al., 2024). When employees perceive high levels of interpersonal justice, they are more likely to feel valued, trusted, and psychologically safe, which in turn fosters positive attitudes and organizational behaviors (Rahaman et al., 2022). Conversely, mistreatment, rudeness, or a

lack of respect can undermine trust, erode commitment, and increase the likelihood of conflict or counterproductive work behaviors (Thomson et al., 2021).

Key aspects of interpersonal justice include respectful treatment, dignity, and the absence of abusive behavior (Meyer et al., 2018; Samosh et al., 2023). Respectful treatment involves acknowledging employees' contributions and interacting with them courteously. Dignity refers to recognizing employees as worthy individuals whose opinions and rights matter in the workplace (Atmaji et al., 2023). Importantly, interpersonal justice also encompasses fairness in social interactions during decision-making processes, where the manner of delivery can be as influential as the decisions themselves. Even when outcomes or processes are perceived as fair, insensitive or disrespectful communication can negate the positive effects of distributive or procedural justice (Atmaji et al., 2023). This highlights the interrelated nature of justice dimensions, where interpersonal fairness strengthens or weakens the overall perception of organizational justice (Knapp et al., 2019).

Interpersonal justice is particularly critical in contexts such as performance appraisals, conflict resolution, disciplinary actions, or organizational change initiatives (Liao et al., 2024). During these interactions, employees are acutely aware of how authority figures treat them, and perceptions of respect or disrespect can shape both immediate reactions and long-term attitudes (Zagenczyk et al., 2021). For example, employees who receive negative performance feedback in a respectful, supportive manner are more likely to accept the outcome, view the organization positively, and engage in constructive behaviors (Rahaman et al., 2022). Conversely, feedback delivered in a dismissive, rude, or humiliating manner can lead to resentment, disengagement, and withdrawal, regardless of the evaluation's fairness (Dar & Rahman, 2019; Greco et al., 2019). Studies also show that interpersonal justice strongly predicts trust in management,

organizational commitment, and willingness to engage in organizational citizenship behaviors, highlighting its significance as a driver of positive organizational outcomes (Rahman, 2024).

Interpersonal justice is an essential dimension of organizational justice, focusing on the quality of interpersonal treatment employees receive in the workplace (Molines et al., 2025). By emphasizing respect, dignity, and sensitivity in interactions, organizations can foster trust, strengthen relationships between employees and supervisors, and support overall engagement and commitment (Rahaman et al., 2022). It operates synergistically with other dimensions of justice, reinforcing the effects of fair outcomes, processes, and information, and is particularly important during sensitive or high-stakes organizational interactions (Sarfraz et al., 2018). Recognizing and promoting interpersonal justice is essential for organizations seeking to maintain a favorable workplace climate, reduce conflict, and enhance employee satisfaction and performance.

Procedural Justice

Procedural justice concerns how employees evaluate the fairness of organizational processes, including whether procedures are applied consistently to people and remain stable over time (van Dijke et al., 2018). While distributive justice focuses on the equity of rewards or outcomes (Xu et al., 2024), procedural justice emphasizes the mechanisms through which those outcomes are determined (Roch et al., 2019). Employees are sensitive not only to what they receive but also to whether the methods, rules, and decision-making processes that lead to those outcomes are perceived as fair and impartial (Pan et al., 2018). This distinction is critical because even favorable outcomes may fail to generate commitment or satisfaction if the processes behind them are perceived as unclear, biased, or inconsistent (Kang & Sung, 2019).

Central to employees' evaluations of procedural fairness are several key elements that shape how organizational processes are interpreted and experienced. These elements, drawn from Colquitt's (2001) framework, include accuracy, voice, consistency, correctability, and bias suppression. Accuracy refers to the extent to which decisions are grounded in complete, reliable, and valid information, ensuring that outcomes are informed by objective evidence rather than assumptions or incomplete data. Voice reflects employees' opportunities to express their views or provide input during decision-making, enhancing perceptions of respect and inclusion even when outcomes are unfavorable. Consistency involves the uniform application of procedures across individuals and over time, reinforcing perceptions that organizational rules are stable and applied equitably. Correctability refers to the availability of mechanisms that allow decisions to be challenged or revised when errors occur, signaling organizational accountability and fairness. Finally, bias suppression emphasizes the importance of neutrality in decision-making, requiring that personal interests, favoritism, or prejudice do not influence procedural outcomes (Colquitt, 2001). Collectively, these elements demonstrate that procedural justice extends beyond formal policies to encompass the fairness, transparency, and integrity of the processes through which organizational decisions are made.

Research consistently demonstrates that procedural fairness is a powerful predictor of employee attitudes and organizational outcomes, often surpassing the influence of distributive fairness (Pan et al., 2018). While fair outcomes are important, employees frequently weigh the fairness of the process more heavily when judging their overall satisfaction and commitment to the organization (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019). For example, even when outcomes are favorable, employees who perceive procedures as arbitrary, inconsistent, or lacking transparency may experience lower job satisfaction, reduced trust in management, and diminished organizational

commitment (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019; Liang & Li, 2019). Conversely, when procedures are perceived as fair, employees are more likely to accept negative outcomes, engage in constructive behaviors, and maintain positive attitudes toward the organization (Pan et al., 2018). This phenomenon is particularly evident in contexts such as performance appraisal, promotions, or disciplinary actions, where perceptions of procedural fairness can determine whether employees perceive the organization as legitimate, ethical, and worthy of their engagement (van Dijke et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2024).

Overall, procedural justice represents a fundamental dimension of organizational justice, highlighting the importance of how decisions are made rather than merely what decisions are made (Kang & Sung, 2019). By emphasizing criteria such as consistency, accuracy, transparency, voice, correctability, and bias suppression, procedural justice provides a structured approach for organizations to build trust, enhance employee satisfaction, and strengthen commitment. Understanding procedural justice is therefore essential for managers, HR professionals, and organizational scholars seeking to foster a fair and productive workplace, and it serves as a critical foundation for research linking organizational justice to employee behavior, motivation, and identification.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a widely studied construct in organizational behavior, reflecting the extent to which employees feel positively about their work and work environment. Job satisfaction refers to an individual's personal evaluation of their feelings about their work, which may vary along a spectrum from dissatisfaction to satisfaction (Judge et al., 2017). An extension of this conceptualization describes job satisfaction as the degree to which people like or dislike their jobs, emphasizing that satisfaction is not limited to emotion but also includes evaluative

judgments (Montañez-Juan et al., 2019). Similarly, the dual cognitive and affective components suggest that employees form judgments about their job while simultaneously experiencing emotional reactions to their work conditions (Malhotra et al., 2022). Collectively, these definitions converge on the idea that job satisfaction represents an overall evaluative assessment of one's job, encompassing both feelings and beliefs about work experiences.

Job satisfaction can be conceptualized at both general and specific levels. At a general level, job satisfaction refers to an employee's overall perception of their job. At a specific level, satisfaction focuses on particular aspects of work (Vincent & Marmo, 2018), such as pay, supervision, coworkers, work tasks, or opportunities for promotion. This distinction is important because employees may be satisfied with certain aspects of their work while dissatisfied with others, which can influence their behavioral and emotional responses (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022). For example, an employee may enjoy their job tasks but feel undervalued in terms of compensation, producing a mixed overall evaluation. Employees continuously assess the fairness of their exchanges with the organization, comparing inputs such as effort, skill, or loyalty to outcomes such as pay, recognition, or career development (Koçak & Kerse, 2022). When employees perceive fairness and reciprocity, their overall job satisfaction is enhanced (Vincent & Marmo, 2018), whereas perceptions of inequity can lead to dissatisfaction, reduced commitment, and disengagement (Solomon et al., 2022).

Job satisfaction is shaped by multiple interrelated factors, which can be broadly categorized into individual, job-related, organizational, and interpersonal dimensions. Individual factors, such as personality traits, play a significant role; for instance, employees high in extraversion often report greater satisfaction due to a natural tendency toward positive affect, whereas those high in neuroticism are more prone to dissatisfaction due to heightened sensitivity

to stressors (Andaraby & Siddiq, 2023). Personal values, expectations, and work–life balance also influence satisfaction, as employees compare their experiences with what they consider desirable or fair (Giessner et al., 2023).

Job-related factors are just as important in shaping satisfaction. The design of tasks, the variety of responsibilities, the workload, the level of autonomy, and the clarity of roles all influence employees' positive perceptions of their work (Judge et al., 2017). Jobs that offer meaningful and challenging tasks with clear expectations tend to increase satisfaction (Judge et al., 2017). Conversely, poorly designed or unclear roles can lead to frustration and disengagement (Hong et al., 2024). Organizational factors also play a significant role in satisfaction, including leadership style (Loi et al., 2014; Mgaiwa, 2023), organizational culture, recognition programs, support systems, and communication practices (Snipes et al., 2024). For example, an empowering leadership style has been consistently associated with higher job satisfaction because of empowerment and recognition, and supportive cultures that emphasize fairness and transparency help reinforce positive perceptions (Giessner et al., 2023).

Interpersonal factors such as coworker relationships, supervisor support, and team climate shape employees' daily experiences and influence satisfaction (Suranata et al., 2025). Positive interactions, collaboration, and a sense of belonging within teams contribute to contentment (Mascarenhas et al., 2022), whereas conflict, lack of support, or poor communication undermine satisfaction (Hughes et al., 2024). These factors interact, meaning that an employee's overall job satisfaction results from the combined effect of personal characteristics, job design, organizational practices, and interpersonal relationships (Jilili & Aini, 2023).

Job satisfaction is associated with a range of behavioral and affective outcomes that influence both individual employees and organizational functioning. From a behavioral perspective, job satisfaction has been linked to organizational citizenship behaviors, turnover intentions, absenteeism, and job performance (Judge et al., 2017; Montañez-Juan et al., 2019). Employees who experience higher levels of job satisfaction are more likely to engage in discretionary behaviors that support organizational effectiveness, such as assisting coworkers, demonstrating cooperation, and assuming extra-role responsibilities (Giessner et al., 2023). Conversely, lower levels of job satisfaction are often associated with withdrawal behaviors, including absenteeism, reduced effort, and diminished productivity (Snipes et al., 2024). Additionally, job satisfaction is also related to important affective outcomes, including employee engagement, morale, and stress levels. Employees who report higher job satisfaction typically demonstrate greater enthusiasm, energy, and psychological resilience in their work roles (Judge et al., 2017). In contrast, dissatisfaction has been associated with increased risk of burnout and emotional exhaustion (Giessner et al., 2023).

Cognitive outcomes are also significant, encompassing organizational commitment, identification, and motivation (Mascarenhas et al., 2022). Employees who are satisfied with their work tend to internalize organizational values, feel a sense of belonging, and maintain a stronger psychological attachment to the organization (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022; Mascarenhas et al., 2022). This alignment between personal and organizational goals promotes sustained effort and engagement, reinforcing performance and overall organizational effectiveness (Judge et al., 2017). In essence, job satisfaction is a critical predictor of both individual well-being (Hong et al., 2024) and organizational outcomes, demonstrating that employees' perceptions of their work

experience have tangible consequences for engagement, commitment, and productivity (Giessner et al., 2023; Judge et al., 2017).

Nonprofit Health and Human Services

Nonprofit health and human service organizations face a distinctive workforce crisis driven by the convergence of compensation constraints, heightened emotional demands, and systemic funding structures, creating a uniquely challenging context for employee outcomes. Nonprofit health and human service organizations, particularly those reliant on government contracts, operate under severe resource constraints that directly limit their ability to compete on compensation. In the nonprofit child welfare sector, for example, government contracts account for more than half of most organizational budgets (Zhao et al., 2025). This structural dependency creates a compensation crisis, as salary competitiveness affects their ability to recruit and retain employees (Zhao et al., 2025). Consequently, nonprofit health and human service employees, who perform emotionally demanding work with vulnerable populations, earn substantially lower wages than their counterparts in for-profit sectors, creating a fundamental tension between mission commitment and financial survival (West, 2022).

The emotional labor inherent in nonprofit health and human service work intensifies these structural challenges and contributes to conditions that shape employee attitudes and job satisfaction. Social service professionals routinely encounter hardship, poverty, neglect, abuse, and systemic barriers, often absorbing emotional strain without adequate organizational support or access to mental health resources (Zhao et al., 2025). These demands are frequently compounded by understaffing, as turnover driven by compensation limitations increases caseloads for remaining employees, accelerating burnout and diminishing organizational commitment (West, 2022). In this environment, employee perceptions and psychological

experiences become particularly influential in shaping workplace outcomes, as nonprofit organizations rely heavily on employee engagement, resilience, and sustained commitment to fulfill mission-driven objectives (Berlan et al., 2024).

In this context, organizational identification is a critical psychological mechanism that influences job satisfaction and retention. Employees who strongly identify with their organization are more likely to internalize its mission, perceive their work as meaningful, and experience alignment between personal and organizational values (Nunes et al., 2024). This dynamic is especially salient in nonprofit settings, where intrinsic motivation and purpose often compensate for limited extrinsic rewards. Research suggests that strong organizational identification fosters commitment, enhances intrinsic motivation, and promotes resilience, thereby mitigating burnout and supporting higher levels of job satisfaction in environments characterized by emotional demands and heavy workloads (Lai & Nguyen, 2025; Nunes et al., 2024). Understanding the role of organizational identification is therefore essential for explaining how nonprofit health and human service employees maintain engagement despite structural constraints.

Alongside organizational identification, perceptions of fairness, as represented by the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, procedural), provide an important foundation for understanding job satisfaction in nonprofit settings. Because nonprofit organizations frequently operate under constrained budgets, high caseloads, and external regulatory pressures, employee evaluations of fairness may influence attitudes and satisfaction beyond material rewards alone (Kim & Peng, 2018). These justice dimensions collectively shape employees' interpretations of organizational decisions, leadership behaviors, and communication practices, ultimately influencing trust, commitment, and satisfaction (Silard,

2020). Prior research demonstrates that these justice dimensions are significant predictors of job satisfaction (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019), and their influence may be particularly pronounced in nonprofit health and human service organizations, where mission-driven work depends heavily on employee goodwill and perceptions of organizational integrity.

Taken together, the nonprofit health and human service context provides a meaningful setting for examining job satisfaction as an outcome shaped not only by structural conditions but also by psychological and perceptual factors. Organizational identification and perceptions of organizational justice offer important explanatory mechanisms through which employees interpret a demanding work environment, maintain commitment, and evaluate their overall work experience. Examining these factors within nonprofit health and human service organizations contributes to a deeper understanding of how job satisfaction is sustained in organizations characterized by high emotional labor, limited resources, and a strong mission orientation.

Synthesis of the Literature

The literature on organizational justice, organizational identification, and job satisfaction reveals interrelated patterns that underscore the importance of fairness and belonging in shaping employees' attitudes and behaviors. Research consistently positions organizational justice as a foundation for understanding employee responses to their work environments, with decades of scholarship showing that fair procedures, equitable outcomes, respectful interpersonal treatment, and transparent communication predict higher job satisfaction, organizational commitment, engagement, performance, and well-being (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019; Colquitt, 2001; Desrumaux et al., 2023; Pan et al., 2018). These findings align with Social Exchange Theory, which suggests that employees reciprocate fair treatment with positive attitudes and behaviors (Greco et al., 2019; Roch et al., 2019). However, the effects of justice are not uniform. Interactional and

informational justice often prove more influential than procedural or distributive justice in contexts marked by uncertainty or heavy service demands, such as healthcare, nonprofits, and crises (Hughes et al., 2024; Kurdoglu, 2020; Zhao & Zhang, 2024). Moreover, justice frequently operates through indirect pathways, influencing burnout, job embeddedness, perceived support, and organizational commitment before affecting satisfaction and retention (Dechawatanapaisal, 2018; Malla & Malla, 2024). These nuances illustrate that perceptions of fairness are multidimensional, context-dependent, and embedded in broader relational processes.

Across the literature, organizational identification acts as a psychological link that connects justice to job-related outcomes. Based on Social Identity Theory, organizational identification shows how much employees see themselves through their organizational membership and adopt organizational values (Mael & Ashforth, 1992). Justice signifies respect, dignity, and worth, which enhances identification and leads to greater satisfaction, commitment, engagement, and citizenship behavior (Farid et al., 2019; Haynie et al., 2019; Koçak & Kerse, 2022; Zagenczyk & Powell, 2023). Recent research also indicates that identification is a multi-level concept influenced by individual and shared feelings of belonging, which together affect team-level satisfaction and turnover rates (Avanzi et al., 2023). Although identification usually results in positive outcomes, it can also increase stress or burnout in demanding environments when fairness norms are weak, emphasizing the conditional nature of its benefits (De Giorgio et al., 2023; Vásquez-Trespalcios et al., 2023). This pattern underscores the reciprocal relationship between justice and identity. Fair treatment strengthens identification, but identification only improves well-being when it exists within a supportive, fair environment (Vásquez-Trespalcios et al., 2023).

Job satisfaction, long recognized as a critical organizational outcome (Judge et al., 2017), is powerfully shaped by both organizational justice and organizational identification. The literature consistently shows that employees who experience fairness and feel a sense of belonging report higher satisfaction across a wide range of industries and cultural contexts (Loi et al., 2014; Rahman, 2024; Snipes et al., 2024; Yuan et al., 2016). Studies increasingly reveal that justice and identification jointly predict satisfaction, with identification often mediating the justice–satisfaction relationship, suggesting that fairness enhances satisfaction in part by strengthening employees’ psychological connection to the organization (Koçak & Kerse, 2022; Malhotra et al., 2022). However, satisfaction is also shaped by contextual factors such as leadership style, work design, perceived support, and autonomy, which may either amplify or diminish the effects of justice and identification (Montañez-Juan et al., 2019; Rahaman et al., 2022; Solomon et al., 2022). These patterns indicate that job satisfaction emerges from a combination of structural, relational, and psychological conditions.

The nonprofit health and human service organizations offer a unique context that both reinforces and complicates these relationships. Employees in these settings often face resource scarcity, heavy emotional labor, and mission-driven expectations. These conditions heighten the importance of justice and identification for satisfaction and retention (Costakis et al., 2021; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). Research shows that nonprofit workers frequently prioritize mission alignment and relational fairness over material rewards, making procedural fairness and respectful interpersonal treatment especially salient predictors of satisfaction (Almog-Bar et al., 2024; Berlan et al., 2024). Organizational changes, such as mergers or collaborative partnerships, further underscore the centrality of communication and justice norms in preserving trust and identification during periods of uncertainty (Giessner et al., 2023; Kim & Peng, 2018). Despite

these insights, studies also reveal inconsistencies, including variation in which justice dimensions matter most, differences across sectors in how justice influences satisfaction, and contradictory evidence regarding whether identification buffers or worsens strain in demanding contexts (Nunes et al., 2024; Vásquez-Trespacios et al., 2023). These inconsistencies point to the need for more integrative and context-sensitive models.

Research Opportunities

A synthesis of the literature on the four dimensions of organizational justice, organizational identification, and job satisfaction reveals substantial evidence of interrelationships among them. However, gaps remain, particularly in nonprofit and human service settings. Although extensive research supports the positive influence of justice on satisfaction (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019; Xu et al., 2024) and the mediating role of organizational identification in employee attitudes (Afrahi et al., 2025; Avanzi et al., 2023; Loi et al., 2014), few studies examine these constructs together within the unique constraints of nonprofit health and human service organizations. Research on nonprofits indicates that employees may prioritize mission alignment, relational fairness, and identification differently than workers in other sectors (Berlan et al., 2024; Nunes et al., 2024; Vincent & Marmo, 2018), yet the mechanisms linking organizational justice, organizational identification, and job satisfaction remain largely unexplored in this context. Furthermore, although studies acknowledge that fairness and workplace identity may function differently under conditions of scarcity, emotional labor, or crisis (Almog-Bar et al., 2024; Costakis et al., 2021), scholars have not empirically integrated these elements into a single model. Addressing this gap is important because nonprofit health and human service organizations face persistent turnover, burnout, and recruitment challenges, underscoring the need to understand how fairness and identification shape employee

commitment and satisfaction in mission-driven work environments. Filling this gap offers the opportunity to refine theoretical models of organizational justice and organizational identification, apply them to resource-constrained nonprofit settings, and provide actionable insights that strengthen workforce stability in one of the country's most essential service sectors.

Contradictions in the Literature

Some studies identify procedural justice as the strongest predictor of satisfaction and legitimacy (Liang & Li, 2019; Xu et al., 2024), while others argue that interactional justice plays the dominant role, especially during times of uncertainty or crisis (Hughes et al., 2024; Kurdoglu, 2020; Lane & Aplin-Houtz, 2023). Research in nonprofit and human service settings further complicates this picture, suggesting that interactional justice may compensate for low distributive justice when mission alignment is strong (Berlan et al., 2024; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). These inconsistencies raise questions about whether the dimensions of organizational justice operate differently in mission-driven organizations than in public or corporate environments.

Organizational identification is generally linked to positive outcomes, including job satisfaction, engagement, and retention (Kundi et al., 2023; Loi et al., 2014; Mascarenhas et al., 2022). However, other studies show that strong identification may intensify employee strain or burnout under high demands (De Giorgio et al., 2023; Vásquez-Trespalcios et al., 2023). Similarly, some research suggests that identification buffers the adverse effects of stress or injustice (Dechawatanapaisal, 2018), whereas others find that it magnifies distress when employees feel morally or emotionally overextended (Silard, 2020). These contradictory patterns suggest that identification may not uniformly benefit employees and may depend heavily on contextual supports, such as justice, leadership, or communication.

Identified Knowledge Gaps

The literature review reveals several areas where research remains limited or absent. First, although organizational justice and organizational identification have been extensively researched, very few studies integrate these constructs to explain job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Most research isolates a single construct or examines partial relationships, leaving a notable gap in understanding how these variables operate together within a larger system (Liao et al., 2024; Malhotra et al., 2022). Second, nonprofit research often highlights challenges such as emotional labor, strained resources, racial pay inequities, and collaborative pressures (Almog-Bar et al., 2024; Costakis et al., 2021; Zhao & Zhang, 2024), yet empirical models rarely examine how perceptions of justice or identification interact with these structural conditions. Studies acknowledge these pressures but do not analyze how they influence the relationship among justice, identification, and satisfaction.

Third, the literature lacks comprehensive models that explain how mission alignment, a central feature of nonprofit work, shapes identification and perceptions of justice (Berlan et al., 2024; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). Additionally, most identification measures were developed in corporate or educational settings (Caputo et al., 2024; Mael & Ashforth, 1992), creating a measurement gap regarding their applicability to human service nonprofits, where identity may be tied to client populations as much as to organizational structures. Lastly, the existing literature does not adequately address how justice and identification function in environments where employees often face high emotional demands and limited material rewards. This omission is significant because human service nonprofits experience chronic turnover, and understanding these mechanisms may inform workforce retention strategies.

Proposed Research

Drawing on the literature, the proposed research seeks to address the lack of integrative models linking the four dimensions of organizational justice, organizational identification, and job satisfaction in nonprofit health human service organizations. Prior research consistently supports the relevance of justice for work attitudes (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019; Xu et al., 2024) and the role of identification in shaping satisfaction, engagement, and retention (Avanzi et al., 2023; Loi et al., 2014). Studies also highlight the unique contextual pressures faced by nonprofit health and human service workers, including emotional labor, resource constraints, and mission-driven expectations (Almog-Bar et al., 2024; Costakis et al., 2021). However, the current literature has not integrated these insights into a unified framework that explains how perceptions of distributive, informational, interactional, and procedural justice, along with organizational identity, jointly shape job satisfaction in this sector.

This study addresses this gap by examining the relationships among procedural justice, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, organizational identification, and job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service organizations, providing insights into how these constructs interact in mission-driven work contexts. In doing so, this study contributes to social exchange theory and offers practical guidance for nonprofit leaders to address retention and organizational stability. By integrating the four dimensions of organizational justice and organizational identification into a single predictive model, the study advances the understanding of the relative influence of these factors on job satisfaction in an under-examined sector. Ultimately, this research responds to calls for more comprehensive examinations of organizational justice in nonprofit settings and establishes a foundation for future inquiry into the mechanisms shaping employee attitudes in resource-constrained, service-oriented environments.

Summary

Chapter 2 examined the theoretical and empirical foundations of this study by reviewing the literature on the four dimensions of organizational justice, organizational identification, and job satisfaction among full-time employees in health and human service organizations, using social exchange theory as a framework. Through a synthesis of the literature, gaps were identified, including the absence of integrated models linking the four dimensions of justice, organizational identification, and job satisfaction in nonprofit contexts. These gaps underscore the need for the present study, which examines how the four dimensions of organizational justice and organizational identification predict job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Building on the insights outlined in this chapter, Chapter 3 describes the methodology used to investigate these relationships and address the limitations identified in the current literature.

CHAPTER 3. METHODOLOGY

Chapter 3 presents the methodology used to investigate how organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice predict job satisfaction among full-time nonprofit employees in health and human services organizations. The general problem guiding this study is that nonprofit health and human service organizations continue to face persistent challenges with employee job satisfaction, which can reduce organizational stability and service quality (Lian et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2024). The purpose of this quantitative, predictive, correlational study was to examine the statistical relationships among five predictor variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) and job satisfaction to better understand which factors contribute most strongly to employees' perceptions of their work experience, in nonprofit health and human services. This chapter details the research design and rationale, describes the population and sampling strategy, outlines the variables and instruments used to measure each construct, and explains the data collection procedures, ethical considerations, and analytic techniques that guide the study. Collectively, these components provide a transparent and rigorous methodological foundation for addressing the project's research question and interpreting the study's findings with appropriate scholarly caution.

Research Questions and Design

The following research questions were asked to determine whether organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in the health and human services sector.

RQ1: To what extent does the overall model of organizational identification, distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations?

H₀₁: The variables of organizational identification, procedural justice, interpersonal justice, informational justice, and distributive justice do not predict job satisfaction.

H_{a1}: The variables of organizational identification, procedural justice, interpersonal justice, informational justice, and distributive justice do predict job satisfaction.

RQ2: Which variables (organizational identification, distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) significantly predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations?

H₀₂: Organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice do not significantly predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

H_{a2}: At least one of the variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, or procedural justice) significantly predicts job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

RQ3: Which variable is the strongest predictor of job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations?

H₀₃: None of the predictor variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) is a significantly stronger predictor of job satisfaction than the others among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

H_{a3}: At least one predictor variable (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, or procedural justice) is a significantly stronger predictor of job satisfaction than the others among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

This study employed a quantitative, predictive correlational design to examine the extent to which organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural) predicted job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. A quantitative approach was chosen because the study aimed to analyze the relationships among variables on a single outcome variable. Consistent with Creswell and Creswell (2018), quantitative methods are well-suited for examining relationships among variables using standardized measurement instruments. Predictive correlational design allowed for the use of multiple linear regression to determine the extent to which the predictor variables explained the variance in job satisfaction and to assess the relative contribution of each predictor. Survey-based measures enabled efficient data collection for a large sample of nonprofit health and human service employees across the United States.

Although the quantitative approach has strengths like objectivity, generalizability, and the ability to test relationships statistically, it also has limitations. Quantitative designs may oversimplify complex workplace experiences and cannot capture the depth of emotions, context, or meaning that qualitative data would provide (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). However, a qualitative design was not suitable for this study because the research questions did not aim to explore lived experiences or subjective interpretations. Instead, the focus was on measuring and predicting relationships between predefined variables. To improve the design, multiple validated instruments with proven reliability and validity were used, and procedures such as standardized

Likert scales, required-response logic in SurveyMonkey Audience, and a priori power analysis were implemented to minimize threats to validity.

The design was built on the positivist belief that knowledge is gained through objective measurement and empirical analysis. This aligned with the goal of using numerical data to test theoretical predictions. By using validated scales, the study minimized measurement error and improved both internal and external validity. Using SurveyMonkey Audience ensured consistent data collection methods and reduced the chance of missing responses, which increased reliability. This design effectively addressed the research question by statistically testing whether, and how much, organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice predicted job satisfaction. The use of multiple linear regression allowed for examining both the overall predictive power of the variables and the unique effect of each predictor. This provided a thorough understanding of the factors that influence job satisfaction within nonprofit health and human service organizations. Overall, the design was well-suited to the research goal, demonstrated strong methodology, and allowed for clear interpretation of the relationships among the study variables.

Sampling

This section explains the sampling strategy used to recruit participants for this quantitative, predictive, correlational study examining how organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice predict job satisfaction among full-time nonprofit employees in health and human service organizations. Since the study aimed to analyze statistical relationships among these variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice), it was important to recruit a sample that accurately reflects individuals working in

nonprofit health and human service organizations who can provide meaningful responses about their workplace experiences. The sampling method ensured that participants met the inclusion criteria and had enough exposure to their organization to give informed perceptions of job satisfaction and justice.

Sample and Population

For this study, the population includes full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. This group is of interest because employees are likely to develop informed perceptions of organizational identification, organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural), and job satisfaction. According to Vincent and Marmo's (2018) finding that nonprofit workers make up the third-largest segment of employees in the U.S., the population for this study is sizable and diverse, covering individuals in various nonprofit health and human service roles, demographic backgrounds, and organizational settings.

Since surveying the entire population is not feasible, a sample of individuals was recruited for this study. The sampling method employed was non-probability convenience sampling through the SurveyMonkey Audience feature, targeting participants who meet the inclusion criteria: (a) full-time nonprofit employees in health and human services, and (b) employed in the U.S. This approach is justified by practical constraints and the need to efficiently access a sufficiently large and diverse group of participants. Although this sampling method does not guarantee a perfectly representative cross-section of the entire population, it allows for data collection from individuals directly relevant to the research questions, whose responses can offer meaningful insights into the relationships among organizational identification, the four dimensions of organizational justice, and job satisfaction.

Sample Size Rationale

For this quantitative, predictive, correlational study, the required sample size was determined via an a priori power analysis to ensure adequate statistical power for the planned multiple linear regression. Power analysis is a widely accepted method for determining sample size in quantitative research because it allows researchers to estimate the number of participants needed to detect statistically meaningful relationships among variables while reducing the risk of Type I and Type II errors (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Because this study examined the predictive relationship between five independent variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) and job satisfaction, it was essential to obtain a sample large enough to detect a moderate effect within a regression model.

Using G*Power with the test family Linear Multiple Regression: Fixed Model, R^2 Deviation from Zero, and an effect size of $f^2 = 0.15$, an alpha level of 0.05, and a desired power of 0.80, the analysis indicated a minimum sample size of 92 participants. This number is the smallest needed to detect a statistically significant relationship between the predictor variables and job satisfaction, with an 80% chance of avoiding a Type II error. However, to account for possible participant attrition, incomplete responses, and the practical issues of online survey research, a second power analysis was performed using the same parameters, but with the statistical power increased to 0.99. A power level of 0.99 greatly reduces the chance of a Type II error. Under these settings, G*Power suggested a sample size of 184 participants, which became the target for this study. Using this larger sample improves the stability of the regression model, increases the accuracy of parameter estimates, and aligns with methodological recommendations that prioritize maximizing power.

Procedures

This section outlines the step-by-step procedures for conducting the study, from preparation through data collection and management. The procedures describe how the research was implemented in line with the selected methodology, including recruitment, informed consent, survey implementation, and processes to ensure consistency, reliability, and ethical integrity throughout the study. Each step is detailed to ensure sufficient clarity and transparency for other researchers to replicate the study.

Participant Selection

This study employed purposive sampling, which is appropriate for research requiring participants who meet specific, predefined characteristics aligned with the study's purpose. Purposive sampling enabled the targeted selection of full-time employees in health and human services organizations who met the inclusion criteria to address the research questions. Because the characteristics required for this study are specific and cannot be randomly sampled from the general population, purposive sampling was used to ensure that only qualified participants were invited. Participants were recruited through SurveyMonkey Audience, an online platform for data collection and participant recruitment. The recruitment site remains de-identified in accordance with dissertation anonymity standards; however, the platform matches researchers' specified inclusion criteria with potential participants from its national participant pool. The site enables filtering by industry, employment characteristics, and geographic location to identify individuals who meet established eligibility criteria. There was no direct contact or interaction with potential participants at any point during recruitment.

A SurveyMonkey Audience account was created and set up to support the recruitment of participants for the study. Recruitment parameters were configured to target full-time employees

working within nonprofit health and human service organizations, and SurveyMonkey Audience automatically applied a geographic filter to restrict responses to individuals working in nonprofit organizations and located within the United States. An incidence rate was chosen based on the expected challenge of finding individuals who met the study's specific inclusion criteria. After configuring the recruitment settings, the survey was finalized during the design phase. The eligibility screening question was shown first, followed by the informed consent document, the demographic question, and the survey instruments. Once the survey was designed, recruitment commenced through SurveyMonkey Audience's pay-per-participant model. A total of 220 participant responses were purchased to ensure the minimum required sample size of 184 completed and eligible responses was reached.

Before reviewing the informed consent document, participants were asked a single screening question to determine their eligibility for the study. The question asked: "Do you work in the Health & Human Services field? (e.g., includes mental health/counseling services, behavioral health, disability support services, foster care programs, child welfare services, housing services, food insecurity programs, community development, after-school programs, juvenile justice, child advocacy, early intervention, public health education, substance use treatment, domestic violence services, refugee & immigrant support, senior services, crisis hotlines/services). Participants had to answer this eligibility question to continue. Those who responded indicating they did not meet the criteria were automatically disqualified and received a message thanking them and letting them know their responses did not qualify. Disqualified individuals could not proceed with the survey or access any other study materials beyond this question.

Participants who met all eligibility criteria were directed to the informed consent page. The informed consent document clearly outlined the study purpose, procedures, voluntary nature of participation, risks, benefits, and the absence of researcher-provided incentives. Participants were also informed that SurveyMonkey donates \$0.50 to a charity of their choice upon completing surveys, a standard practice for SurveyMonkey Audience studies. Participants indicated their willingness to participate by selecting the “I agree” option. Those who disagreed were ineligible to participate in the survey and were not enrolled. After consent, participants advanced to the demographics section, which asked for their sex (male, female, prefer not to respond).

Data Collection

Following consent and completion of the demographic question, eligible participants completed the online survey administered through SurveyMonkey Audience. Recruitment emails were distributed by SurveyMonkey Audience to panel members who met the established inclusion criteria. A total of 220 responses were purchased; however, SurveyMonkey Audience allowed 251 completed responses before closing the survey.

The survey included three validated instruments. Organizational identification was measured with Mael and Ashforth’s Organizational Identification Scale (1992). Perceptions of organizational justice were assessed using Colquitt’s Organizational Justice Scale (2001), which measures distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice. Job satisfaction was measured using the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Weiss et al., 1999). The full survey took approximately eight minutes to complete. Participants completed the study in one session, and no follow-up data collection was required.

After data collection concluded, the dataset was exported from SurveyMonkey Audience and imported into JASP statistical software for analysis. Prior to conducting statistical tests, the dataset was screened for completeness, missing values, straight-line responses, and outliers, as well as the assumptions required for multiple linear regression analyses. Following data screening, the final analytic sample included 186 participants. All data were stored securely in accordance with Capella University requirements. Electronic data were saved on a flash drive, with sole access to this researcher, and participants were identified by alphanumeric identifiers (P1-P186) to maintain anonymity. Data will be retained for seven years in accordance with institutional policy. After this period, electronic data will be permanently erased using Darik's Boot and Nuke (DBAN) data-erasure software.

Instruments

This quantitative correlational study used three validated instruments to measure organizational identification, organizational justice, and job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Each instrument was selected for its theoretical relevance, psychometric strength, and widespread use in organizational research.

Mael & Ashforth's Organizational Identification Scale

Mael and Ashforth's Organizational Identification Scale (1992) is a six-item Likert-type questionnaire designed to operationalize the construct of organizational identification. Participants respond to items on a scale from 1 (*very dissatisfied*) to 5 (*very satisfied*). The scale generates an interval-level composite score by averaging all six items, with higher scores indicating greater organizational identification. The instrument is widely regarded as one of the most frequently used measures of organizational identification in the literature (Boroş, 2008).

Although permission was not required to use the instrument, permission was provided by Dr. Blake Ashforth, with no special qualifications required for administration.

Validity. The Organizational Identification Scale (Mael & Ashforth, 1992) has shown strong convergent and divergent validity. Caputo et al. (2024) reported convergent validity with well-being outcomes ($r = .581$) and divergent validity with emotional exhaustion ($r = .143$), supporting the scale's ability to represent the intended construct accurately. The validation studies used samples of working adults across various organizational contexts, supporting its applicability in nonprofit settings.

Reliability. Reliability has been consistently established through Cronbach's alpha. Mael and Ashforth's scale (1992) reported a Cronbach's alpha of .87, exceeding the commonly accepted threshold of .80 for acceptable internal consistency. This level of reliability indicates that the instrument consistently measures organizational identification across different samples and contexts.

Applicability. Given the scale's strong psychometric properties and its direct alignment with the study variable, the Organizational Identification Scale (Mael & Ashforth, 1992) was appropriate for measuring participants' perceptions of organizational identification. Its brevity, clarity, and established use in organizational research support its suitability for an online survey of health and human services employees.

Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale

Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale is a 20-item instrument designed to measure four dimensions of organizational justice: distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural. Each item is rated on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (to a *very small extent*) to 5 (to a *very large extent*) (Colquitt, 2001). Four items measure distributive justice, reflecting employees'

perceptions of the fairness of organizational outcomes such as pay, rewards, and workload relative to their contributions. Five items measure informational justice, assessing perceptions of the adequacy, honesty, and timeliness of explanations provided regarding organizational decisions. Four items measure interpersonal justice, capturing the extent to which employees feel they are treated with dignity, politeness, and respect by supervisors or decision makers. Seven items measure procedural justice, reflecting perceptions of the fairness of the procedures used to make decisions and allocate outcomes (Colquitt, 2001). These subscale scores were calculated by averaging the items corresponding to each justice dimension. This instrument is widely used in organizational behavior research due to its multidimensional structure and strong psychometric properties. Although formal permission was not required to use this instrument, Dr. Jason Colquitt confirmed that the scale may be used for research purposes and that no specific qualifications are required for its administration.

Validity. Colquitt's (2001) scale has demonstrated robust convergent and divergent validity. Convergent validity scores for all justice dimensions exceed $r > .50$, indicating strong relationships between scale components and related constructs (Omar et al., 2018). Divergent validity was supported by Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values that exceeded correlations with other organizational constructs, confirming that each justice subscale measures a distinct facet of organizational justice.

Reliability. The internal consistency reliability of Colquitt's (2001) scale is well established, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from .92 to .94 for the total scale. Subscale reliability values are 0.92 for distributive and procedural justice, 0.94 for informational justice, and 0.93 for interpersonal justice (Omar et al., 2018). These values exceed the .80 threshold, indicating excellent reliability across all dimensions.

Applicability. Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale (2001) aligns directly with the study's predictor variables related to perceptions of fairness in nonprofit health and human services organizations. Its detailed, multidimensional structure enables a comprehensive examination of organizational justice and supports predictive analyses of job satisfaction. The scale's extensive validation and reliability make it appropriate for use with this population.

Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire- Short Form

The Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) (Weiss et al., 1999) short form is a widely used instrument that measures intrinsic, extrinsic, and general job satisfaction. The short form contains 20 items, with responses measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*very dissatisfied*) to 5 (*very satisfied*). The MSQ (Weiss et al., 1999) assessed satisfaction across multiple facets, including achievement, recognition, independence, supervision, working conditions, and others. It generated interval-level data suitable for quantitative statistical analysis, including correlational and regression models. Permission to use the MSQ (Weiss et al., 1999) is granted under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License, with no specialized qualifications required for administration.

Validity. The MSQ (Weiss et al., 1999) demonstrates strong construct validity, with confirmatory factor analysis yielding internal construct validity of .58 (Mgaiwa, 2023). These values fall within the recommended range (.50 to .70), indicating adequate construct representation. The instrument has been validated across diverse work settings, supporting its use with nonprofit health and human services employees.

Reliability. Internal consistency reliability for the MSQ (Weiss et al., 1999) short form ranges from .85 to .91 (Guion, 1977), exceeding the recommended minimum of .80. These

values confirm the instrument's stable measurement properties and its suitability for assessing job satisfaction across diverse populations.

Applicability. The MSQ (Weiss et al., 1999) was selected to operationalize job satisfaction because it aligns directly with the study's dependent variable and has been extensively validated for use with working adults. Its multidimensional assessment provides nuanced insights into satisfaction levels, making it suitable for predictive correlational analyses examining relationships with organizational identification and perceptions of justice.

Data Analysis

This study explored how organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. The study included five predictor variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) and one outcome variable: job satisfaction. All predictor variables were measured on Likert-type scales at the interval or continuous level, and the overall job satisfaction was also measured at this level. Prior to analyses, MSQ (Weiss et al., 1999) items were reverse-coded in JASP to ensure that higher values indicated higher levels of job satisfaction. Because the research questions focused on the predictive capacity of multiple independent variables for a single dependent variable, multiple linear regression (MLR) was used as the analytic method. MLR was chosen because it allows simultaneous analysis of how several independent variables influence a single dependent variable while accounting for shared variance among predictors. All analyses were performed using JASP.

Research Question 1 (RQ1) examined the extent to which the overall model of organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and

procedural justice predicted job satisfaction among full-time employees in health and human service organizations. Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to determine whether the combined set of predictor variables significantly explained variance in job satisfaction. The overall model fit was evaluated using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) associated with the regression model. Adjusted R^2 was examined to assess the proportion of variance in job satisfaction explained by the predictors collectively. The statistical significance of the overall regression model was evaluated using the associated F statistic and p -value, with significance determined at the 0.05 level.

Research Question 2 (RQ2) examined which variables among organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice significantly predicted job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the predictive relationships between the independent variables and job satisfaction. Individual regression coefficients were examined to determine the unique contribution of each predictor while controlling for the influence of the other variables in the model. Standardized beta coefficients (β) were used to allow comparison across predictors measured on different scales. Statistical significance for each predictor was evaluated using the associated p -values, with significance determined at the .05 level. Predictors with statistically significant beta weights were interpreted as uniquely contributing to the prediction of job satisfaction, beyond the effects of the other predictors included in the model. Non-significant beta weights indicated that the predictor did not explain a unique portion of variance in job satisfaction when the remaining variables were held constant.

Research Question 3 (RQ3) sought to determine which variable served as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction among the independent variables. To address this question, the same multiple linear regression model used for RQ2 was examined. Rather than employing stepwise or hierarchical regression procedures, the relative strength of predictors was determined by comparing standardized beta coefficients (β) within the full regression model. Standardized beta coefficients were used because they place predictors on a common metric, allowing direct comparison of the magnitude of each predictor's relationship with job satisfaction while controlling for other variables in the model. The predictor with the largest statistically significant standardized beta coefficient was interpreted as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction. This approach was selected to maintain theoretical consistency with social exchange theory and to avoid data-driven model selection procedures associated with stepwise regression.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive analyses were performed to summarize the sample's characteristics (sex). Frequencies and percentages were calculated for the demographic variable, and the results were displayed in the demographics table. Visual summaries, including histograms, boxplots, and Q–Q plots, were also created to examine the distribution of the study variables and identify potential outliers. These steps supported the assessment of the assumptions needed for predictive correlational analyses and were conducted in JASP.

Hypotheses and Assumption Testing

This study included three research questions and associated hypotheses that evaluated the predictive relationship between the five independent variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) and job satisfaction. Multiple linear regression (MLR) was selected as the primary inferential statistical

method because it allows simultaneous evaluation of all predictors and determination of their individual and combined effects on the outcome variable. Before evaluating the hypotheses, the eight underlying assumptions of MLR were tested to ensure the analysis's appropriateness and validity. The assumptions and the procedures used to assess them are described below.

Linearity. The assumption of linearity requires that the relationship between each predictor variable and the dependent variable be linear. Linearity was assessed through visual inspection of the residual plot generated in JASP. This plot was examined to determine whether the relationships between the predictor variables and job satisfaction followed a linear pattern.

Independence of Errors. Independence of errors refers to the absence of autocorrelation among residuals. This assumption was evaluated using Durbin–Watson statistic. Durbin-Watson values between 1.5 and 2.5 were considered indicative of independent residuals.

Homoscedasticity. Homoscedasticity refers to the requirement that residuals exhibit constant variance across levels of the predicted outcome variable. The assumption was assessed by examining scatterplots of standardized residuals against predicted values. A random and evenly distributed pattern of residuals indicated that the assumption of homoscedasticity was met.

Normality of Residuals. The assumption of normality requires that regression residuals be approximately normally distributed. Normality was evaluated using histograms and normal probability (Q-Q) plots of the residuals generated in JASP.

Absence of Multicollinearity. Multicollinearity occurs when predictor variables are highly correlated with one another, which can distort regression estimates. Multicollinearity was assessed using Pearson correlation metrics, variance inflation factors (VIF), and tolerance

statistics. Correlation coefficients approaching .80 or higher, VIF values greater than 10, or tolerance values below .10 were considered indicators of problematic multicollinearity.

Outliers and Influential Observations. Outliers and influential observations were assessed using standardized residuals, Cook's distance, and leverage. Standardized residuals with absolute values greater than 3, Cook's distance values approaching or exceeding one, and high leverage values were examined to determine whether influential cases required further evaluation.

Level of Measurement. Multiple linear regression requires that the dependent variable be continuous and that the independent variables be continuous or properly coded categorical variables. In this study, the dependent variable (job satisfaction) and predictor variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) were measured using Likert-type scales and treated as continuous variables for the purposes of regression analysis. Variable coding was verified during the data preparation process.

Model Specification. The model specification refers to the inclusion of appropriate predictor variables supported by theory and empirical evidence. The regression model for this study included organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice as predictors of job satisfaction, consistent with the study's conceptual framework and relevant literature.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the *Belmont Report* (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979), which emphasizes respect for persons, beneficence, and justice.

Prior to data collection, approval was obtained from the Capella University Institutional Review Board (IRB), and no data were collected until formal approval was granted. The study also adhered to the ethical standards outlined in the American Psychological Association Ethical Principles of Psychologists and Code of Conduct (APA, 2024), particularly those related to informed consent, confidentiality, and respect for participant rights and dignity.

Participants first answered a screening question to determine eligibility before accessing the informed consent form. Electronic consent was obtained before participation, and individuals were required to indicate their agreement before proceeding to the demographic question and the survey. The informed consent document described the study's purpose, procedures, the voluntary nature of participation, potential risks and benefits, and the estimated time needed to complete the survey. Data were collected through SurveyMonkey Audience, an online panel that recruits respondents meeting specific inclusion criteria. Although formal permission was not required, Blake Ashforth and Jason Colquitt confirmed that their respective instruments may be used for research purposes without special qualifications for administration. The Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Weiss et al., 1999) is available under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License and does not require specialized qualifications for administration. Because participation occurred in a virtual setting, the informed consent and screening questions clearly outlined the eligibility requirements, helping participants accurately assess their eligibility for the study. Participants who did not meet the inclusion criteria were not allowed to proceed to the survey.

Participation in the study was voluntary, and participants were informed that they could withdraw from the survey at any time without penalty. The survey included general questions about professional experiences and took about eight minutes to complete. No sensitive

psychological, medical, or personally identifiable questions were asked, and the study was not expected to pose physical, emotional, social, legal, or employment-related risks. Participants did not receive payment from the researcher; however, in accordance with SurveyMonkey Audience procedures, SurveyMonkey donated \$0.50 to a charity chosen by each participant.

Protecting participants' confidentiality and privacy was a priority throughout the study. To maintain anonymity, each participant was assigned a unique alphanumeric code (P1-P186), which was used in the dataset. All data were exported from SurveyMonkey Audience and stored securely in accordance with federal and institutional guidelines. Research data will be retained for seven years and then permanently destroyed using DBAN (Darik's Boot and Nuke) data-scrubbing software.

Participants were asked to report their sex as part of the demographic information used for descriptive statistics. Demographic data were reported in aggregate form and were not used to identify individual participants. The target population (full-time employees working in nonprofit health and human service organizations) does not qualify as a vulnerable population under federal guidelines. Nonetheless, safeguards were implemented to ensure that participation was free from coercion or undue influence. There were no professional, supervisory, or personal relationships with participants recruited through SurveyMonkey Audience, and this researcher had no financial, professional, or personal conflicts of interest related to the study.

This study was classified as minimal risk under federal research regulations, meaning participation involved no greater risk than those typically encountered in daily life or routine psychological assessments. Participants were informed of the study's nature and purpose before taking part and had the option to decline or stop at any time without penalty. The main burden for participants was the time needed to complete the survey. No personally identifiable

information was collected, and all responses were recorded anonymously to further reduce potential risks to participants. Overall, the procedures used in this study ensured that participants could make an informed decision about participating and that their rights, dignity, and well-being were protected throughout the research.

Summary

This chapter provided a comprehensive description of the methodological framework used to examine how organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice predicted job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human organizations. The chapter outlined the quantitative, predictive-correlational design, which was selected to evaluate the statistical relationships among the study variables and to determine their combined and unique contributions to job satisfaction. The population, sampling strategy, and sample size rationale were detailed, including the use of SurveyMonkey Audience to recruit participants who met the study's inclusion criteria and an a priori power analysis to ensure sufficient statistical power.

Chapter 3 further described procedures for participant selection, informed consent, survey administration, and data management, emphasizing steps to ensure ethical compliance, confidentiality, and methodological rigor. The validated instruments for measuring organizational identification, organizational justice, and job satisfaction were presented, along with evidence of their reliability and validity. Finally, Chapter 3 outlined the planned analytic approach, including descriptive statistics, assumption testing, and multiple linear regression to evaluate the predictive relationships central to the research questions. Collectively, the chapter established a transparent and replicable methodological foundation for the study.

Chapter 4 outlines the statistical analyses performed using the methods described in Chapter 3. The chapter begins with an overview of the sample demographics, followed by an assessment of the assumptions underlying multiple linear regression and descriptive statistics. The results of the multiple linear regression analyses addressing each research question are then presented. The chapter concludes with a summary of the main findings.

CHAPTER 4. RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of statistical analyses examining the relationships among organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, procedural justice, and job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Chapter 4 includes a description of participant demographics, an assessment of the assumptions of multiple linear regression, and the results of hypothesis testing for each research question. Results are presented objectively without interpretation.

Description of the Sample

The population for this study consisted of full-time nonprofit health and human service employees in the United States. A total of 251 participants completed the survey. An a priori power analysis conducted using G*Power indicated that a minimum of 184 participants would be needed to detect a medium effect size with a power of 0.99 and an alpha level of 0.05. During data screening, 65 participants were removed because they showed no variability across items, indicating straight lining. The final sample included 186 participants. The survey gathered demographic data, including sex. All participants confirmed their eligibility through a screening question administered via SurveyMonkey Audience and provided informed consent before answering the demographic (sex) question and starting the survey.

Table 1 presents the distribution of participants by sex for the 186 participants in this study. Of the total sample, 48.4% were male ($n = 90$), 51.1% were female ($n = 95$), and 0.5% ($n = 1$) preferred not to respond to this question. The distribution reflects a relatively balanced representation of male and female participants within the sample. No responses were missing for this item. Sex was collected for descriptive and contextual purposes to characterize the study sample. However, it was not included as a predictor or control variable in the regression analyses

used to test this study’s hypotheses. As a result, sex was not examined in relation to job satisfaction or the primary study variables.

Table 1
Sex Distribution of Participants

Sex	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	95	51.1	51.1	51.1
Male	90	48.4	48.4	99.5
Prefer not to respond	1	0.5	0.5	100.0
Missing	0	0.0		
Total	186	100.0		

Presentation of Data and Analysis

This study investigated three research questions, each with its own null and alternative hypotheses. During multiple linear regression, eight assumptions were assessed to test the data used to address the research questions. The eight assumptions for a multiple linear regression are level of measurement, model specification, linearity, homoscedasticity, presence of outliers, independence of errors, normality of residuals, and multicollinearity. The level of measurement assumption requires that the dependent variable be continuous and that the independent variables be continuous or appropriately dummy-coded categorical variables. This assumption was satisfied because all predictors and the outcome variable were measured on continuous Likert-type scales. Verification of variable coding was performed during data cleaning. Model specification was evaluated to ensure that all relevant predictors were included and that no extraneous variables were included. The regression model consisted solely of the five theoretically and empirically supported predictors identified in the literature, supporting the appropriateness of the model specification.

Independence of errors was assessed using the Durbin–Watson statistic, as shown in Table 2. The Durbin-Watson statistic for the final regression model (M_1) was 1.83, which falls within the acceptable range (1.5–2.5). The associated test was not statistically significant ($p = .242$), further indicating that the residuals were independent. Additionally, the autocorrelation value (0.084) was close to zero, providing further evidence that the errors were not systematically related. Together, these results support the conclusion that the assumption of independence of errors was satisfied for the multiple linear regression model predicting job satisfaction.

Table 2
Model Summary for the Multiple Linear Regression Predicting Job Satisfaction

Model	R	R^2	Adjusted R^2	RMSE	Durbin-Watson		
					Autocorrelation	Statistic	p
M_0	0.000	.000	.000	0.515	-0.014	2.015	.918
M_1	0.738	.544	.531	0.352	0.084	1.830	.242

A visual inspection of the residuals-versus-predicted values plot was conducted to assess the assumptions of linearity, homoscedasticity, and the absence of outliers. The residuals were randomly distributed around zero with no evident curvilinear pattern, indicating that the linearity assumption was met. The spread of residuals appeared relatively constant across levels of predicted values, supporting the homoscedasticity assumption. No extreme outliers were observed, as standardized residuals fell within acceptable limits. Additionally, Cook’s distance values were all below 1.0, indicating that no influential observations were present. Therefore, the assumptions of linearity, homoscedasticity, and the absence of influential outliers were considered satisfied (Figure 1).

Figure 1
Residuals Versus Predicted Values

Normality of the residuals was first evaluated by visual inspection of the histogram of standardized residuals (Figure 2). The distribution appears approximately bell-shaped and centered around zero, indicating that the residuals are reasonably symmetric. Although minor skewness and slight deviations at the tails were visible, the overall pattern did not suggest substantial departures from normality. No extreme residual values were evident, as standardized residuals remained within acceptable limits. Since multiple linear regression assumes normally distributed residuals to ensure accurate standard errors and significance testing, these findings support that the normality assumption was adequately satisfied.

Figure 2
Histogram of Standardized Residuals

Normality was further evaluated using a normal probability (Q-Q) plot of standardized residuals (Figure 3). This Q-Q plot compares the observed residual distribution to the expected theoretical distribution under normality. As shown in Figure 3, the points closely follow the diagonal reference line, indicating that a normal distribution accurately represents the observed residuals. Although slight deviations appear at the lower and upper tails, these are minimal and do not indicate significant skewness or kurtosis. There is no pronounced curvature or systematic pattern suggesting meaningful non-normality. Because the assumption of normally distributed residuals is essential for the correct estimation of standard errors and hypothesis testing in multiple linear regression, the Q-Q plot provides additional evidence that this assumption of normality was adequately met for the model predicting job satisfaction.

Figure 3

Normal Q-Q Plot of Standardized Residuals

Table 3 presents the regression coefficients for the model predicting job satisfaction from organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural). Multicollinearity was assessed using tolerance and variance inflation factor (VIF) values from the coefficient output for the full regression model (Table 3). Multicollinearity occurs when predictor variables are highly correlated, which can inflate standard errors and destabilize regression coefficient estimates. Table 3 shows tolerance values ranging from .283 to .852 and VIF values ranging from 1.174 to 3.539. These values were within acceptable limits (tolerance values $> .10$ and VIF values well below commonly cited concern thresholds of 5–10), indicating that multicollinearity was not a threat to the interpretation of the regression coefficients. These results suggest that the predictors (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) were sufficiently distinct from one another to allow reliable estimation of their unique effects on job satisfaction. Therefore, the assumption of no problematic multicollinearity was considered satisfied.

Table 3*Regression Coefficients for Predictors of Job Satisfaction*

Model		<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Collinearity Statistics	
							Tolerance	VIF
M ₀	(Intercept)	4.000	0.038		106.027	< .001		
M ₁	(Intercept)	1.680	0.181		9.282	< .001		
	Organizational Identification	0.177	0.042	.227	4.160	< .001	0.852	1.174
	Distributive Justice	0.083	0.044	.148	1.872	.063	0.407	2.454
	Informational Justice	0.207	0.061	.323	3.409	< .001	0.283	3.539
	Interpersonal Justice	0.130	0.049	.198	2.630	.009	0.447	2.235
	Procedural Justice	0.040	0.055	.056	0.720	.473	0.424	2.358

Overall, all assumptions required for multiple linear regression were carefully evaluated before hypothesis testing. The assumptions of level of measurement and model specification were satisfied through appropriate variable coding and the inclusion of theoretically grounded predictors. Visual inspection of diagnostic plots supported the assumptions of linearity, homoscedasticity, and the absence of influential outliers. Independence of errors was confirmed using the Durbin-Watson statistic. Normality of residuals was supported by both the standardized residuals histogram and the Q-Q plot, which indicated no substantial deviations from a normal distribution. Finally, collinearity statistics demonstrated that multicollinearity was not a concern, as tolerance and VIF values fell within recommended thresholds. Collectively, these findings indicate that the data met the statistical assumptions necessary for multiple linear regression, which supports the validity and interpretability of the regression analysis conducted to address this study's research questions.

Hypothesis Testing

After verifying that the assumptions of multiple linear regression were satisfied, hypothesis testing was conducted to address the study's research questions. Multiple linear regression analyses were used to examine whether the overall model significantly predicted job satisfaction, whether organizational identification and the dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) significantly predicted job satisfaction, and which variable emerged as the strongest predictor.

RQ1: To what extent does the overall model of organizational identification, distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations?

H₀₁: The variables of organizational identification, procedural justice, interpersonal justice, informational justice, and distributive justice do not predict job satisfaction.

H_{a1}: The variables of organizational identification, procedural justice, interpersonal justice, informational justice, and distributive justice do predict job satisfaction.

To answer RQ1, the overall multiple linear regression model was statistically significant, indicating that the predictors collectively explained variance in job satisfaction, $F(5, 180) = 42.95, p < .001$, as shown in Table 4. The results indicated that the five predictor variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) collectively accounted for a statistically significant proportion of the variance in job satisfaction. Consistent with the model summary results (adjusted $R^2 = .531$), the predictors accounted for 53.1% of the variance in job satisfaction (Table 2). Based on these results, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_{a1}) was supported.

Table 4*Analysis of Variance for the Regression Model Predicting Job Satisfaction*

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
M ₁	Regression	26.64	5	5.328	42.94	< .001
	Residual	22.33	180	0.124		
	Total	48.98	185			

RQ2: Which variables (organizational identification, distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) significantly predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations?

H₀₂: Organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice do not significantly predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

H_{a2}: At least one of the variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, or procedural justice) significantly predicts job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

Results from Table 3 indicated that organizational identification, informational justice, and interpersonal justice were significant predictors of job satisfaction. Organizational identification significantly predicted job satisfaction ($B = 0.177$, $SE = 0.042$, $\beta = .227$, $t = 4.106$, $p < .001$), indicating that higher levels of organizational identification were associated with higher job satisfaction when controlling for the other variables in the model. Informational justice also significantly predicted job satisfaction ($B = 0.207$, $SE = 0.061$, $\beta = .323$, $t = 3.409$, $p < .001$), suggesting that higher perceptions of informational justice were associated with higher job satisfaction. Interpersonal justice was another significant predictor ($B = 0.13$, $SE = 0.049$, $\beta = .198$, $t = 2.630$, $p = .009$), indicating that higher levels of respectful and dignified interpersonal

treatment were associated with higher job satisfaction. In contrast, distributive justice ($B = 0.083$, $SE = 0.044$, $\beta = .148$, $t = 1.872$, $p = .063$) and procedural justice ($B = 0.040$, $SE = 0.055$, $\beta = .056$, $t = .720$, $p = .473$) were not statistically significant when controlling for other variables in the model. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) was rejected, indicating that at least one predictor in the model significantly predicted job satisfaction.

RQ3: Which variable is the strongest predictor of job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations?

H₀₃: None of the predictor variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) is a significantly stronger predictor of job satisfaction than the others among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

H_{a3}: At least one predictor variable (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, or procedural justice) is a significantly stronger predictor of job satisfaction than the others among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

Research Question 3 examined which predictor variable was the strongest predictor of job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. To address this question, standardized regression coefficients (β) were examined to compare the relative strength of each predictor while controlling for the influence of the remaining variables in the model. Comparison of standardized coefficients indicated that informational justice was the strongest predictor of job satisfaction ($\beta = .323$, $p < .001$), with the largest unique contribution to the prediction of job satisfaction among the variables included in the model. This finding indicates that perceptions regarding adequacy, honesty, and clarity of information

communication within the organization played the most influential role in predicting employees' job satisfaction among the variables included in the model. Organizational identification ($\beta = .227, p < .001$) and interpersonal justice ($\beta = .198, p = .009$) also contributed significantly to predicting job satisfaction, although their standardized effects were smaller than that of informational justice. In contrast, distributive justice ($\beta = .148, p = .063$) and procedural justice ($\beta = .056, p = .473$) were not statistically significant predictors when variables were considered simultaneously in the model. Based on the comparison of standardized coefficients, informational justice emerged as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction among the variables examined. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) was rejected, indicating that at least one predictor variable was more strongly associated with job satisfaction than the others.

Summary

This chapter presented the results of data analyses conducted to address the research questions examining relationships among organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, procedural justice, and job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Before hypothesis testing, the assumptions of multiple linear regression were evaluated and found to be satisfactorily met. Results of the multiple linear regression analyses indicated that the overall model significantly predicted job satisfaction, and that organizational identification, informational justice, and interpersonal justice were significant predictors, even after controlling for the remaining variables. Informational justice emerged as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction based on the relative magnitude of the standardized regression coefficients. Chapter 5 interprets these findings within the context of the existing literature and theoretical framework, discusses

implications for practice and future research, addresses study limitations, and presents recommendations derived from the study results.

CHAPTER 5. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

This chapter explores the interpretation and implications of the findings reported in Chapter 4. The purpose of this study was to examine how organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, procedural) influence job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Social exchange theory provided the framework for this quantitative cross-sectional design and multiple linear regression analysis, assessing the combined and individual contributions of these predictors to job satisfaction. By analyzing these variables within a single predictive model, this study adds to the limited research on how the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) and organizational identification interact to shape job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service organizations. This chapter begins with a summary of the main findings, followed by a discussion of the results in relation to the theoretical framework, research questions, and existing literature. It also covers the study's limitations, implications for policy and practice, and recommendations for future research, as well as a summary of the study's contributions to understanding job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

Summary of Findings

The purpose of the study was to examine how organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to determine whether organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice significantly predicted job satisfaction, to evaluate the overall model's explanatory power, and to identify which predictor variable emerged as the

strongest. Items within the MSQ (Weiss et al., 1999) were reverse-coded prior to analysis to ensure that all items were oriented in the same direction, so that higher scores reflected higher levels of job satisfaction.

Results showed that the overall regression model significantly predicted job satisfaction, with organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, procedural) collectively explaining 53.1% of the variance in job satisfaction (adjusted $R^2 = .531$). This finding indicates that employees' perceptions of their connection to the organization and fairness in organizational processes and interactions play an important role in shaping job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service settings. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) for RQ1 was rejected.

Among individual predictors, organizational identification, informational justice, and interpersonal justice were statistically significant predictors of job satisfaction (RQ2). Employees who reported stronger organizational identification and who perceived communication processes and interpersonal treatment as fair and respectful reported higher job satisfaction. Because at least one predictor variable significantly predicted job satisfaction, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) for RQ2 was rejected. In contrast, distributive justice and procedural justice did not significantly predict job satisfaction when all predictors were considered simultaneously in the regression model. These findings indicate that relational and communication-based aspects of informational justice may be more influential for job satisfaction than outcome-based or procedural considerations in nonprofit health and human service organizations. The non-significant beta coefficients for distributive justice and procedural justice indicated that these variables did not explain a unique portion of variance in job satisfaction when the remaining predictors were held constant.

Finally, comparison of standardized regression coefficients indicated that informational justice was the strongest predictor of job satisfaction among the variables examined (RQ3). Although organizational identification and interpersonal justice also contributed significantly to the model, informational justice had the largest unique effect, suggesting that employees' perceptions of transparent, timely, and adequate communication are particularly influential in shaping job satisfaction. Because informational justice demonstrated the strongest standardized effect among the predictors, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) for RQ3 was rejected. Distributive and procedural justice showed weaker, non-significant effects when other predictors were included in the model.

Overall, the findings suggest that job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations is most strongly linked to employees' perceptions of communication fairness (informational justice), interpersonal treatment (interpersonal justice), and their psychological connection to the organization (organizational identification), emphasizing the importance of relational and informational dynamics within the organizational environment. This highlights the significance of how employees receive communication, are informed about decisions, and are treated by leaders and colleagues, as these elements play a crucial role in shaping their overall attitudes toward work. In mission-driven nonprofit settings, where financial incentives and structural resources may be limited, transparent communication and respectful interpersonal interactions can be especially meaningful. Additionally, a strong sense of organizational identification may strengthen an employee's connection to their organization's mission and values, further boosting job satisfaction. Collectively, these findings underscore the importance of fostering supportive communication practices, respectful

workplace relationships, and a shared sense of purpose to improve employee satisfaction within nonprofit health and human service organizations.

Findings in Context of the Theoretical Framework

This study was guided by social exchange theory, which details how reciprocal exchanges between employees and the organization shape relationships within organizations (Roch et al., 2024; Straatmann et al., 2020). According to this framework, employees develop attitudes and behaviors based on their perceptions of how fairly and respectfully they are treated, and positive organizational treatment is expected to result in positive employee outcomes, such as increased commitment and job satisfaction (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022). The findings of this study provide empirical support for applying social exchange theory in nonprofit health and human service organizations.

The significant relationship between organizational identification and job satisfaction aligns with social exchange theory's emphasis on reciprocity and mutual investment (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022). Employees who perceive alignment between their personal identities and organizational values may be more likely to interpret organizational support and fairness as indicators of a positive exchange relationship. In response, employees reciprocate by developing more favorable attitudes toward their work, including higher levels of job satisfaction (Dar & Rahman, 2019). This finding suggests that organizational identification is an important psychological mechanism through which social exchange processes influence employees' attitudes.

The findings related to organizational justice further support this theoretical framework. Informational justice emerged as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction, indicating that employees place substantial value on transparent, timely, and adequate communication from

organizational leaders. Within the context of social exchange theory, clear and honest communication may signal respect, trust, and organizational investment in employees, strengthening the perceived quality of the exchange relationship. Similarly, the significant relationship between interpersonal justice and job satisfaction suggests that respectful and dignified interpersonal treatment contributes to employees' perceptions of fair exchange, reinforcing positive attitudes toward the organization.

In contrast, distributive justice and procedural justice did not significantly predict job satisfaction when considered alongside the other variables in the model (organizational identification, informational justice, and interpersonal justice). From a social exchange theory perspective, this finding may suggest that employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations prioritize relational and interactional fairness over outcomes or formal procedures alone. Given the mission-driven, service-oriented nature of nonprofit work, employees might respond more to how decisions are communicated and implemented than to the results themselves. These results support social exchange theory by demonstrating that employees' perception of communication fairness and respectful interpersonal treatment may strengthen reciprocal relationships with the organization, thereby influencing job satisfaction.

Findings in Context of the Research Questions and Hypotheses

The findings of this study provide meaningful insight into each research question and hypothesis by clarifying the collective and individual contributions of the predictor variables (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, and procedural justice) to job satisfaction. Overall, the results support the premise that employees' perceptions of fairness (organizational justice) and their psychological connection (organizational identification) to the organization are associated with job satisfaction and

indicate that not all dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) contribute equally to job satisfaction within a single predictive model.

Regarding RQ1, the results showed that the overall regression model significantly predicted job satisfaction, thus rejecting the null hypothesis (H_{01}). Organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice together accounted for a considerable portion of the variance in job satisfaction, indicating that these factors jointly influence employee attitudes. This finding supports the original research question by demonstrating that it is not just a single organizational factor, but a combination of relational and perceptual experiences within the organization that contribute to employees' job satisfaction. The significant model suggests that examining organizational identification and perceptions of organizational justice together offers a meaningful framework for understanding employee satisfaction in this sector.

In RQ2, the focus was on the unique predictive contributions of each variable. The findings partially supported expectations: organizational identification, informational justice, and interpersonal justice emerged as statistically significant predictors, whereas distributive justice and procedural justice did not show significant unique effects when all predictors were considered simultaneously. These non-significant standardized beta coefficients indicate that distributive justice and procedural justice did not explain a unique portion of variance in job satisfaction when the remaining variables were held constant. The lack of statistical significance does not suggest that distributive and procedural justice are unimportant or unrelated to job satisfaction. Rather, the findings indicate that their predictive influence may overlap with or be accounted for by other variables in the model, particularly those reflecting relational and communication-based aspects of fairness. These results suggest that the absence of statistical

significance should not be interpreted as evidence that distributive or procedural justice should be excluded from future research; rather, their role may be more indirect or context-dependent within nonprofit organizational environments. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) was rejected since at least one predictor variable significantly contributed to explaining job satisfaction.

The findings for RQ3 further clarified the relative importance of the predictors (organizational identification, distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, procedural justice) by identifying informational justice as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction, based on the magnitude of the standardized beta coefficients. This result indicates that employees' perceptions of transparent, timely, and adequate communication may play a particularly influential role in shaping job satisfaction compared with other organizational factors examined in the study. The rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{03}) for RQ3 suggests that although multiple variables contribute to job satisfaction, some predictors exert stronger effects than others when considered within the same model. This finding highlights the importance of examining the relative strength of predictors rather than relying solely on the overall model significance.

Several methodological or research design factors may also account for the unexpected or non-significant findings. First, the simultaneous inclusion of multiple related predictors in the regression model may have reduced the apparent unique contribution of distributive and procedural justice, given shared variance among organizational justice dimensions. Second, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to examine how perceptions of justice influence job satisfaction over time, potentially obscuring the longer-term effects of procedural or outcome-based fairness. Additionally, reliance on self-report measures may have increased the likelihood that relational perceptions, such as communication quality and interpersonal treatment, were

more salient to participants at the time of survey completion. These considerations suggest that future research may benefit from longitudinal designs or alternative modeling approaches to further examine the distinct roles of organizational justice dimensions.

Overall, the findings meaningfully address the original research questions by demonstrating that organizational identification and relational forms of organizational justice significantly predict job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service employees, and that informational justice emerged as the strongest predictor in the model. Even where hypotheses were only partially supported, the results contribute to a more nuanced understanding of how organizational justice operates within the organizational context and provide direction for future research examining the complex relationships among organizational identification, justice perceptions, and employee attitudes.

Findings in the Context of the Previous Literature

The results of this study generally align with the broader literature indicating that organizational identification and dimensions of organizational justice are meaningful predictors of employee job satisfaction (Colquitt, 2001; Desrumaux et al., 2023; Judge et al., 2017; Yuan et al., 2016). Consistent with social exchange theory, the overall regression model significantly predicted job satisfaction and explained a substantial proportion of variance, suggesting that employees' perceptions of fairness and their psychological connection to the organization function together as important determinants of job attitudes (Cropanzano et al., 2022; Greco et al., 2019; Roch et al., 2019). This finding aligns with prior research emphasizing that perceptions of justice shape trust, legitimacy, and satisfaction by signaling whether the organization values and respects its members (Kang & Sung, 2019; Straatmann et al., 2020). The strength of the overall model also reinforces the argument in the nonprofit literature that perceptions of fairness

and belonging can be especially influential in settings characterized by emotional labor and resource constraints (Berlan et al., 2024; Costakis et al., 2021; Vincent & Marmo, 2018).

The significant relationship between organizational identification and job satisfaction aligns with prior studies showing that employees who internalize organizational membership and perceive value congruence report stronger commitment and higher satisfaction (Afrahi et al., 2025; Dechawatanapaisal, 2018; Mael & Ashforth, 1992). This finding also aligns with social identity perspectives outlined in Chapter 2, which propose that individuals derive a meaningful part of their self-concept from organizational membership, strengthening motivation and favorable attitudes when employees feel psychologically connected to the organization (Lin & Liu, 2019; Zagenczyk et al., 2021). In nonprofit health and human service organizations, prior research suggests that identification may be particularly important because employees often place a high value on mission alignment and collective purpose (Lai & Nguyen, 2025; Nunes et al., 2024). The present findings extend this literature by demonstrating that organizational identification remained a significant predictor even when multiple dimensions of organizational justice were considered simultaneously, indicating that identification contributes to job satisfaction alongside relational justice factors, particularly informational and interpersonal justice.

Findings on organizational justice both confirm and refine prior research. Across the broader justice literature, all four dimensions have frequently been linked to job satisfaction and related outcomes (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019; Colquitt, 2001; Shehadeh, 2023; Xu et al., 2024). However, this study's results indicate that the influence of justice dimensions is not uniform, consistent with the literature synthesis in Chapter 2, which notes that informational and interpersonal forms of justice often emerge as particularly salient in high-demand service

contexts marked by uncertainty (Hughes et al., 2024; Kurdoglu, 2020; Lane & Aplin-Houtz, 2023). Specifically, informational justice was the strongest predictor of job satisfaction, and interpersonal justice also contributed significantly. These findings closely mirror prior work emphasizing that employees respond strongly to the quality of explanations, transparency, and respectful treatment because these elements communicate dignity, trustworthiness, and organizational support (Kurdoglu, 2020; Rahaman et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2024). In nonprofit environments, where material rewards may be constrained, the literature suggests that relational fairness and communication can compensate for limited distributive outcomes (Berlan et al., 2024; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). The present results support this idea by indicating that what leaders communicate and how they treat employees may be more directly tied to job satisfaction than procedural outcomes when all dimensions are considered together.

At the same time, the non-significant findings for distributive and procedural justice partially diverge from prior research identifying procedural justice as a strong predictor of satisfaction, legitimacy, and commitment (Liang & Li, 2019; Pan et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2024). Rather than contradicting the justice literature broadly, this pattern aligns with the contradictions described in Chapter 2. Different studies identify different justice dimensions as most important, often depending on the organizational context (Hughes et al., 2024; Kurdoglu, 2020; Lane & Aplin-Houtz, 2023). In mission-driven nonprofit health and human service organizations, employees may tolerate limited outcomes or imperfect procedures when the interpersonal and informational environment signals respect, trust, and shared purpose (Berlan et al., 2024; Kim & Peng, 2018; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). Another plausible explanation is methodological and statistical rather than conceptual. Because justice dimensions are interrelated, distributive and procedural justice may share variance with informational and interpersonal justice, reducing their

unique predictive contribution when all variables are included simultaneously (Colquitt, 2001; Knapp et al., 2019). In other words, distributive and procedural justice may still matter. However, their effects may operate indirectly, overlap with relational dimensions, or become more visible under different conditions, such as organizational change, conflict, or performance-related decisions, as the literature suggests (Hughes et al., 2024; Liao et al., 2024).

Overall, this study contributes to the existing literature by providing an integrated test of organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice as predictors of job satisfaction within nonprofit health and human service contexts, an area identified in Chapter 2 as underexplored despite persistent workforce challenges (Almog-Bar et al., 2024; Berlan et al., 2024; Costakis et al., 2021). The findings extend current understanding in two meaningful ways. First, they support prior claims that fairness (organizational justice) and (organizational) identification jointly shape job satisfaction, while demonstrating that identification retains unique predictive value beyond perceptions of justice (Koçak & Kerse, 2022; Malhotra et al., 2022). Second, they refine justice scholarship in nonprofit settings by showing that communication fairness (informational justice) and respectful treatment (interpersonal justice) may be especially influential drivers of job satisfaction relative to distributive and procedural elements when examined within a single model (Hughes et al., 2024; Kurdoglu, 2020; Vincent & Marmo, 2018). Taken together, these results reinforce the view that job satisfaction emerges from a combination of psychological attachment and day-to-day relational experiences, and that, in mission-driven service environments, informational and interpersonal exchanges may be particularly central mechanisms underlying satisfaction and retention.

Limitations

Although this study provides meaningful insight into the relationships among organizational identification, the four dimensions of organizational justice, and job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service organizations, several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings. These limitations primarily relate to research design, data collection procedures, and sampling approach, and they influence the scope of interpretation and the generalizability of the results. Recognizing these constraints enhances the rigor and transparency of the research process and situates the findings within appropriate methodological boundaries.

The use of a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design limits the depth of understanding of participants' experiences and perceptions. While quantitative methods enable the statistical examination of relationships among variables and support generalizability to larger samples, they do not capture the contextual or experiential factors that may influence job satisfaction. Qualitative or mixed-methods approaches may have provided additional insight into how employees interpret fairness, communication, and organizational identification within nonprofit health and human service settings. Additionally, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference or assessment of changes in perceptions over time, as data were collected at a single point in time rather than longitudinally.

Another limitation concerns reliance on self-reported data. Participants self-selected for the study and completed survey measures reflecting their perceptions and experiences. Self-report methods can introduce response bias, including social desirability bias, inaccurate recall, and intentional misrepresentation. Although participants were informed that the study was voluntary and confidential, some individuals may not have fully or accurately reported their attitudes or experiences. Similarly, although SurveyMonkey Audience applied recruitment filters

intended to identify full-time nonprofit health and human service employees, eligibility ultimately relied on participants' self-reports. The single screening question asked participants whether they worked in the health and human services field, with examples provided to help them determine eligibility. As a result, some participants may have misidentified themselves as belonging to the target population, potentially introducing error.

A third limitation emerged during the initial recruitment process. Initially, additional eligibility criteria required that participants have been employed in their current role for at least 6 months and not be on a performance improvement plan or any other human resources-related intervention. However, these criteria substantially reduced the participant pool, prompting SurveyMonkey Audience to cancel the study due to an insufficient number of eligible respondents. Consequently, these criteria were removed to allow recruitment to proceed. While this adjustment enabled completion of data collection, it may have increased variability within the sample by including employees with varying levels of organizational tenure or current employment circumstances, which could influence perceptions of organizational justice, organizational identification, and job satisfaction. Future research may benefit from reintroducing these criteria or examining tenure and employment status as control variables.

Convenience sampling through an online participant panel also represents a limitation. Although SurveyMonkey Audience provided access to a targeted population and applied demographic filters, participants were not randomly selected from the broader population of nonprofit health and human service employees. As a result, the sample may not fully represent all employees in this sector, limiting the generalizability of the findings beyond individuals willing to participate in online survey panels. A probability-based sampling approach or

recruitment through specific nonprofit organizations may strengthen external validity in future studies.

Lastly, several delimitations should be noted. The study focused exclusively on full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. It did not examine part-time employees, volunteers, or employees in for-profit or government human service settings. Additionally, demographic information such as sex was collected for descriptive purposes only and was not analyzed as an independent variable, which may have limited the ability to examine potential group differences in perceptions of organizational justice or job satisfaction (Grund et al., 2023). Including additional demographic or organizational variables, such as tenure, organizational size, or leadership structure, may have provided further insight into factors influencing job satisfaction.

Overall, these limitations reflect practical and methodological considerations rather than flaws that undermine the study's contributions. Recognizing these constraints improves the transparency and rigor of the research process and offers a clearer framework for interpreting the findings within appropriate boundaries. By placing the results within the specific context of nonprofit health and human service organizations, this study provides meaningful insights while clarifying the conditions under which the conclusions should be understood. Considering the limitations not only prevents overgeneralization but also highlights directions for future research aimed at strengthening methodological design, increasing contextual diversity, and further refining the theoretical relationships examined in this study.

Implications for Policy and Practice

The findings of this study have several practical implications for policy and practice in nonprofit health and human service organizations aiming to boost employee satisfaction and,

ultimately, workforce stability. By highlighting organizational identification, informational justice, and interpersonal justice as key predictors of job satisfaction, the results provide concrete guidance for organizational leaders, human resource professionals, and policymakers working to enhance employee experience and retention in resource-constrained, mission-driven settings. These implications are presented with a focus on realistic applications rather than broad or exaggerated claims.

Implications for Organizational Policies and Leadership Practice

The prominence of informational justice as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction suggests that organizational policies should prioritize transparent, timely, and adequate communication. Leaders in nonprofit health and human service organizations may benefit from developing formal communication standards to ensure that employees receive clear explanations of decisions, changes, and organizational priorities. Policies that encourage open dialogue, consistent information sharing, and opportunities for employees to ask questions may enhance perceptions of fairness and trust, which have been linked to positive employee attitudes in prior research (Colquitt, 2001). Even in organizations with limited financial resources, improvements in communication practices represent a feasible strategy for supporting employee satisfaction.

Interpersonal justice also emerged as a significant predictor, indicating that employees' treatment by supervisors and organizational representatives has a meaningful impact on job satisfaction. Organizational policies that emphasize respectful treatment, dignity, and professionalism, particularly in supervisory training and performance evaluation, may contribute to more positive employee perceptions. Leadership development initiatives that focus on relational skills, emotional intelligence, and fair interpersonal conduct may be especially

beneficial in nonprofit settings, where employees often perform emotionally demanding work and rely heavily on supportive workplace relationships.

The significant relationship between organizational identification and job satisfaction further suggests that policies and practices that strengthen employees' sense of connection to the organization may improve workplace outcomes. Leaders may foster organizational identification by clearly communicating organizational values, reinforcing the organization's social mission, and creating opportunities for employees to see how their work contributes to broader community impact. Prior research indicates that when employees perceive alignment between their values and organizational goals, they are more likely to develop positive attitudes and commitment (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022). For nonprofit organizations, reinforcing mission alignment through onboarding, staff meetings, and recognition practices may be particularly effective.

Implications for Human Resource Practices

From a human resources perspective, the findings suggest that job satisfaction interventions should extend beyond compensation and formal procedures. Although distributive and procedural justice did not uniquely predict satisfaction in this study, this does not imply that pay structures or decision-making processes are unimportant. Rather, the findings indicate that relational and informational aspects of fairness may be more salient predictors of satisfaction within nonprofit health and human service organizations. Human resource professionals may consider integrating communication quality and interpersonal treatment into performance management systems, leadership evaluations, and employee feedback processes.

Additionally, employee engagement surveys and climate assessments could benefit from emphasizing fairness in communication and interpersonal respect. Tracking these aspects can

help organizations identify areas needing improvement and inform targeted actions. These practices align with research suggesting that perceptions of justice and social exchange relationships are key in shaping employee attitudes and behaviors (Gambhir & Kkan, 2022).

Implications for Industrial/Organizational Psychology Practices

The findings of this study also have specific implications for the field of Industrial/Organizational psychology. For Industrial/Organizational psychologists working in nonprofit health and human service contexts, the results highlight the importance of assessing and addressing relational and informational dynamics in addition to structural organizational factors. Traditional organizational interventions often focus on job design, compensation systems, or procedural efficiency. However, the present findings suggest that communication practices and interpersonal treatment may be equally influential, if not more so, for job satisfaction in mission-driven organizations.

These findings can inform Industrial/Organizational psychologists in developing leadership training programs, organizational assessments, and employee engagement initiatives that emphasize the social exchange process. The results support the application of social exchange theory as a useful framework for understanding employee attitudes in nonprofit settings and underscore the value of interventions that strengthen perceived reciprocity, respect, and trust between employees and organizations. Furthermore, Industrial/Organizational psychologists conducting organizational diagnostics may consider prioritizing measures of informational and interpersonal justice when evaluating workplace climate and recommending change initiatives.

Broader Implications for Related Disciplines

Beyond Industrial/Organizational psychology, the findings may inform practice in related fields such as nonprofit management, public administration, and organizational leadership. Professionals in these disciplines may apply the study's results by recognizing that employee job satisfaction is influenced not only by outcomes and procedures but also by everyday interactions and communication practices. Policies that promote fairness, respect, and transparency may contribute to more supportive work environments and help address persistent challenges related to employee burnout and turnover in health and human service organizations.

Recommendations for Future Research

The findings of this study offer several opportunities for future research to advance understanding of job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Future studies may extend this work by employing longitudinal or mixed-methods designs to better capture the dynamic, evolving nature of organizational justice and identification processes over time. Additionally, researchers may explore these relationships across nonprofit subsectors, geographic regions, or organizational sizes to assess contextual variability. The study's empirical findings inform recommendations for future research, identify limitations and delimitations, and suggest additional areas for investigation.

Recommendations Developed Directly From the Data

Future research should continue to examine the role of informational and interpersonal justice in shaping employee satisfaction, as these variables emerged as significant predictors, with informational justice showing the strongest relationship with job satisfaction. Additional research may examine which specific components of communication fairness (informational justice) most strongly influence employees' attitudes (e.g., job satisfaction), such as

communication frequency, transparency in decision-making, and opportunities for employee voice. Qualitative or mixed-methods designs may be particularly valuable for extending these findings by providing deeper insight into how employees interpret communication practices and interpersonal treatment within nonprofit organizational contexts. These approaches may offer deeper insight into processes that are not readily captured in quantitative survey data.

Second, future research should further investigate the roles of distributive and procedural justice, which did not show statistically significant unique effects in this study when examined alongside other predictors. Rather than suggesting that these variables are unimportant, the findings indicate that their influence may be indirect or context-dependent. Future studies may identify potential mediating or moderating relationships, such as whether organizational identification or communication practices (informational justice) mediate the relationship between procedural fairness and job satisfaction. Longitudinal research designs may also help determine whether perceptions of procedural or distributive fairness exert stronger effects over time, particularly during periods of organizational change or resource constraints commonly experienced in nonprofit settings.

Recommendations Derived From Study Limitations

Recommendations derived from study limitations also suggest several directions for future research. Because this study relied on self-reported data collected at a single point in time, future research may benefit from longitudinal or multi-source designs that incorporate supervisor evaluations, organizational records, or repeated measures over time to reduce potential response bias and better examine causal relationships. Additionally, future studies may consider implementing more comprehensive eligibility verification procedures or recruiting participants

directly through nonprofit organizations to further ensure alignment with the intended population and improve external validity.

Recommendations Derived From Study Delimitations

Recommendations based on the study's delimitations further suggest expanding the population examined. The current study focused exclusively on full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Future research may benefit from including part-time employees, volunteers, or employees in for-profit or government human service settings to determine whether the relationships identified in this study differ across employment arrangements or organizational structures. Additionally, the demographic variables collected in this study for descriptive purposes could be examined as analytical variables in future research to explore whether perceptions of fairness and organizational identification differ across demographic groups.

Recommendations to Investigate Issues Not Supported by the Data but Relevant to the Research Problem

Future research should investigate issues that were not fully supported by the data but remain theoretically relevant to the research problem. Although distributive and procedural justice were not significant predictors in the current model, their established importance in the organizational justice literature warrants continued examination. Future studies may explore alternative theoretical frameworks or incorporate additional organizational variables, such as leadership style, organizational culture, or perceived organizational support, to better understand how outcome-based and procedural fairness interact with relational dynamics to influence job satisfaction. Collectively, these recommendations provide a foundation for continued investigation into the complex organizational factors that contribute to employee satisfaction

within nonprofit health and human service organizations and support the ongoing development of research grounded in social exchange theory.

Conclusion

This dissertation examined the extent to which organizational identification and the four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, informational, interpersonal, and procedural justice) predicted job satisfaction among full-time employees in nonprofit health and human service organizations. Guided by social exchange theory, the study used a quantitative, cross-sectional design and multiple linear regression analysis to assess both the combined predictive power of the variables and the unique contribution of each predictor. The study addressed three research questions: whether the overall model predicted job satisfaction (RQ1), which predictors uniquely contributed to job satisfaction (RQ2), and which variable emerged as the strongest predictor (RQ3).

Overall, the findings showed that the full model significantly predicted job satisfaction, with an adjusted R^2 of .531, indicating that it explained a substantial portion of the variance. This result supported the conclusion that perceptions of organizational connection and workplace fairness are meaningfully associated with employees' job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service settings (RQ1). Regarding RQ2, the results showed that organizational identification, informational justice, and interpersonal justice were statistically significant predictors of job satisfaction, even after controlling for the other variables in the model. These findings suggest that employees who feel a stronger psychological connection to their organization, perceive communication as transparent and adequate, and experience respectful interpersonal treatment tend to report higher job satisfaction. In contrast, distributive justice and procedural justice did not significantly predict job satisfaction when considered simultaneously

with the other predictors, indicating that not all dimensions of organizational justice contributed equally to explaining satisfaction within this sample.

The findings also provided a clear answer to RQ3. Informational justice emerged as the strongest predictor of job satisfaction, based on the magnitude of the standardized beta coefficients. This outcome suggests that, within nonprofit health and human service organizations, perceived fairness and communication quality may be particularly influential in shaping employees' satisfaction with their work. Taken together, the pattern of results supports the conclusion that relational and communication-based experiences of fairness, along with employees' identification with the organization, appear to be central factors associated with job satisfaction in mission-driven, service-oriented environments.

This study achieved its intended goals by addressing an identified gap in the literature: the limited research examining organizational identification and the four organizational justice dimensions together as predictors of job satisfaction in nonprofit health and human service organizations. By integrating these constructs into a single predictive model, the dissertation contributes to a more context-sensitive understanding of job satisfaction. It extends prior research suggesting that the relative importance of justice may vary across sectors and work environments. In particular, the findings refine the application of social exchange theory by underscoring the salience of informational and interpersonal exchanges in employees' evaluations of the quality of their relationship with the organization.

The implications of these findings are both practical and scholarly. In nonprofit settings where resources may limit financial rewards or structural reforms, improvements in communication practices and interpersonal treatment can serve as achievable and meaningful ways to support employee satisfaction. Simultaneously, the findings indicate that future research

should continue exploring how different justice dimensions function in nonprofit contexts, including whether distributive and procedural justice have indirect effects or become more significant during conditions such as organizational change, high stress, or resource scarcity. Ongoing investigation may also shed light on how organizational identification interacts with perceptions of fairness over time and across various nonprofit subsectors. Overall, this study adds to a more detailed understanding of how relational and informational exchanges influence employee satisfaction in mission-driven environments and provides a basis for further research and practice aimed at strengthening the nonprofit workforce.

REFERENCES

- American Psychological Association. (2024). *Healthy workplaces*.
<https://www.apa.org/topics/healthy-workplaces>
- Afrahi, J., Mutter, A., & Armbrüster, T. (2025). Looking into the black box of employer recommendations: the role of organizational identification and pride. *International Studies of Management and Organization*, 55(3), 327–343.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00208825.2024.2435763>
- Almog-Bar, M., Greenspan, I., Schmid, H., & Oreg, A. (2024). The three P's in nonprofit human service mergers: Strategic response to coping with a crisis. *Human Service Organizations: Management, Leadership & Governance*, 48(3), 305–322.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23303131.2024.2335985>
- Andaraby, A., & Siddiq, A. (2023). Enhancing job satisfaction through motivation and rewards in Afghanistan's public sector banks. *IUP Journal of Bank Management*, 22(3), 46–63.
- Astuti, S. D., & Ingsih, K. (2019). Distributive justice improves job satisfaction and procedural justice increases organizational commitment. *Quality-Access to Success*, 20(169), 93–98.
- Atmaji, Sawitri, H. S. R., Suyono, J., Sarwoto, & Sunaryo, S. (2023). Interpersonal justice, leader-member exchange, and employee negative behaviors: A proposed model and empirical test. *International Journal of Business*, 28(4), 1–26.
[https://doi.org/10.55802/IJB.028\(4\).005](https://doi.org/10.55802/IJB.028(4).005)
- Avanzi, L., Perinelli, E., & Mariani, M. G. (2023). The effect of individual, group, and shared organizational identification on job satisfaction and collective actual turnover. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 53(5), 956–969. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.2946>

- Berlan, D., Lim, S., & Campos, P. D. (2024). Are we on the same page? Individual interpretations of missions within human service nonprofits. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 35(2), 329–351. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21616>
- Boroş, S. (2008). Organizational identification: Theoretical and empirical analyses of competing conceptualizations. *Cognitive Brain Behavior*, 12(1), 1–27.
- Çakiroğlu, D. (2022). Organizational silence's mediation impact on the effect of organizational justice's on intention to quit. *Journal of Business Research*, 14(1), 219–231. <https://doi.org/10.20491/isarder.2022.1376>
- Caputo, A., Gatti, P., Manuti, A., & Cortese, C. G. (2024). Organizational identification: Validation of the Italian scale in the healthcare context. *Bulletin of Applied Psychology*, 82(300), 77–86. <https://doi.org/10.26387/bpa.2024.00010>
- Colquitt, J. A. (2001). On the dimensionality of organizational justice: A construct validation of a measure. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 386–400. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.86.3.386>
- Costakis, H. R., Gruhlke, H., & Su, Y. (2021). Implications of emotional labor on work outcomes of service workers in not-for-profit human service organizations. *Human Service Organizations: Management, Leadership & Governance*, 45(1), 29–48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23303131.2020.1818157>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design* (5th ed.). Sage.
- Cropanzano, R., Skarlicki, D. P., Nadisic, T., Fortin, M., Van Wagoner, P., & Keplinger, K. (2022). When managers become Robin Hoods: A mixed method investigation. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 32(2), 209–242. <https://doi.org/10.1017/beq.2021.16>

- Dar, N., & Rahman, W. (2019). Deviant behaviors and procedural justice: Mediating role of perceived organizational support. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*, 13(1), 104–122.
- Dechawatanapaisal, D. (2018). Nurses' turnover intention: The impact of leader-member exchange, organizational identification and job embeddedness. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 74(6), 1380–1391. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13552>
- De Giorgio, A., Barattucci, M., Teresi, M., Raulli, G., Ballone, C., Ramaci, T., & Pagliaro, S. (2023). Organizational identification as a trigger for personal well-being: Associations with happiness and stress through job outcomes. *Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology*, 33(1), 138–151. <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.2648>
- Desrumaux, P., Moughogha, I. P., Nguema, W. N., & Bouterfas, N. (2023). Impact of organizational justice, support, resilience, and need satisfaction on French social workers' psychological well-being. *Journal of Evidence-Based Social Work*, 20(6), 934–953. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26408066.2023.2232766>
- Farid, T., Iqbal, S., Ma, J., Castro-González, S., Khattak, A., & Khan, M. K. (2019). Employees' perceptions of CSR, work engagement, and organizational citizenship behavior: The mediating effects of organizational justice. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(10), 1731–1747. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16101731>
- Gambhir, V., & Kkan, A. (2022). The influence of organizational justice on organizational politics: A quantitative study. *International Management Review*, 18(1), 35–44.
- Giessner, S. R., Dawson, J. F., Horton, K. E., & West, M. (2023). The impact of supportive leadership on employee outcomes during organizational mergers: An organizational-level

- field study. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 108(4), 686–697.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001042>
- Gong, Z., Ren, M., Sun, Y., Zhang, Z., Zhou, W., & Chen, X. (2025). How does procedural justice affect job crafting? The role of organizational psychological ownership and high-performance work systems. *Behavioral Sciences*, 15(1), 58–73.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/bs15010004>
- Greco, L. M., Whitson, J. A., O’Boyle, E. H., Wang, C. S., & Kim, J. (2019). An eye for an eye? A meta-analysis of negative reciprocity in organizations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 104(9), 1117–1143. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0000396>
- Grund, C., & Tilkes, K. R. (2023). Working time mismatch and job satisfaction—The role of employees’ time autonomy and gender. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 34(20), 4003–4025. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2023.2190036>
- Guion, R. M. (1977). Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. In O. K. Buros (Ed.), *The eighth mental measurements yearbook*. Buros Institute of Mental Measurements
- Haynie, J. J., Flynn, C. B., & Baur, J. E. (2019). The organizational justice-job engagement relationship: How social exchange and identity explain this effect. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 31(1), 28–45.
- Homans, G. C. (1958). Social behavior as exchange. *American Journal of Sociology*, 63(6), 597–606.
- Hong, Y.-H., Ford, M. T., & Jong, J. (2024). Employee benefit availability, use, and subjective evaluation: A meta-analysis of relationships with perceived organizational support, affective organizational commitment, withdrawal, job satisfaction, and well-being. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 109(12), 1921–1947. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001202>

- Hughes, I. M., Keith, M. G., & Gallagher, C. M. (2024). Informational justice, organizational communication, and job insecurity in the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Personnel Psychology*, 23(1), 23–35. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1866-5888/a000325>
- Internal Revenue Service. (2023). *Identifying full-time employees*. <https://www.irs.gov/affordable-care-act/employers/identifying-full-time-employees>
- Jiang, D., Ning, L., & Zhang, Y. (2024). Perceived overqualification as a double-edged sword for employee creativity: The mediating role of job crafting and work withdrawal behavior. *PLoS ONE*, 19(6), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0304529>
- Jilili, M., & Aini, A. (2023). Examining the moderating effect of occupational status on the association of organizational justice and job satisfaction. *Public Organization Review*, 23(1), 97–111. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11115-022-00602-3>
- Judge, T. A., Weiss, H. M., Kammeyer-Mueller, J. D., & Hulin, C. L. (2017). Job attitudes, job satisfaction, and job affect: A century of continuity and of change. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 102(3), 356–374. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0000181>
- Kang, M., & Sung, M. (2019). To leave or not to leave: the effects of perceptions of organizational justice on employee turnover intention via employee-organization relationship and employee job engagement. *Journal of Public Relations Research*, 31(5/6), 152–175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1062726X.2019.1680988>
- Kim, M., & Peng, S. (2018). The dilemma for small human service nonprofits: Engaging in collaborations with limited human resource capacity. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 29(1), 83–103. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21314>

- Knapp, J. R., Sprinkle, T. A., Urick, M. J., & Delaney, K. K. A. (2019). The belonging model of trust. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 30(1), 133–153.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21370>
- Koçak, D., & Kerse, G. (2022). How perceived organizational obstruction influences job satisfaction: The roles of interactional justice and organizational identification. *Sage*, 12(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221079933>
- Kundi, Y. M., Baruch, Y., & Ullah, R. (2023). The impact of discretionary HR practices on knowledge sharing and intention to quit – A three-wave study on the role of career satisfaction, organizational identification, and work engagement. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 34(22), 4205–4231.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2023.2180652>
- Kung, S., Dousin, O., & Biru, A. (2024). Examining the mediating role of perceived organizational support in the relationship between employee motivation and intention to stay: A study of millennials in Malaysia. *Management: Journal of Contemporary Management Issues*, 29(1), 143–152. <https://doi.org/10.30924/mjcmi.29.1.10>
- Kurdoglu, R. S. (2020). The mirage of procedural justice and the primacy of interactional justice in organizations. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 167(3), 495–512.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04166-z>
- Lai, C., & Nguyen, D. T. (2025). The impact of perceived relationship investment and organizational identification on behavioral outcomes in nonprofit organizations: The moderating role of relationship proneness. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 35(3), 527–542. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21632>

- Lane, E., & Aplin-Houtz, M. J. (2023). Informational justice and remote working: All is not fair for work at home. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 35(4), 541–564. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10672-022-09427-0>
- Lian, H., Li, J., Du, C., Wu, W., Xia, Y., & Lee, C. (2022). Disaster or opportunity? How COVID-19-associated changes in environmental uncertainty and job insecurity relate to organizational identification and performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 107(5), 693–706. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001011>
- Liang, J., & Li, X. (2019). Explaining the procedural justice–perceived legitimacy relationship: Relying on relational concern or instrumental concern? *Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology*, 29(3), 193–206. <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.2394>
- Liang, J., & Ma, H. (2021). Interpersonal injustice and perceived legitimacy of authority: The role of institutional trust and informational justice. *Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology*, 31(2), 184–197. <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.2492>
- Liao, Z., Wang, N., Zhu, J., Chen, T., & Johnson, R. E. (2024). Disentangling the relational approach to organizational justice: Meta-analytic and field tests of distinct roles of social exchange and social identity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 109(11), 1716–1731. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001193>
- Lin, Y.-T., & Liu, N.-C. (2019). Corporate citizenship and employee outcomes: Does a high-commitment work system matter? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 156(4), 1079–1097. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-017-3632-1>
- Loi, R., Chan, K. W., & Lam, L. W. (2014). Leader–member exchange, organizational identification, and job satisfaction: A social identity perspective. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 87(1), 42–61. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joop.12028>

- Lorenz, T. (2025). Ethical Leadership: A multi-stage mediation model of value congruence and organizational identification on employee engagement. *Administrative Sciences*, 15(9), 329. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci15090329>
- Mael, F., & Ashforth, B. E. (1992). Alumni and their alma mater: A partial test of the reformulated model of organizational identification. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 13(2), 103–123. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.4030130202>
- Malhotra, N., Sahadev, S., & Sharom, N. Q. (2022). Organizational justice, organizational identification and job involvement: the mediating role of psychological need satisfaction and the moderating role of person-organisation fit. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 33(8), 1526–1561. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2020.1757737>
- Malla, S. S., & Malla, S. (2024). Is organizational justice relevant for enhancing employee's commitment: An empirical analysis using perceiver supervisor support as a mediator. *Social Justice Research*, 37(2), 101–121. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11211-024-00433-1>
- Mascarenhas, C., Galvão, A. R., & Marques, C. S. (2022). How perceived organizational support, identification with organization and work engagement influence job satisfaction: A gender-based perspective. *Administrative Sciences*, 12(2), 66–81. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci12020066>
- Meyer, M., Ohana, M., & Stinglhamber, F. (2018). The impact of supervisor interpersonal justice on supervisor-directed citizenship behaviors in social enterprises: a moderated mediation model. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 29(20), 2927–2948. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1380060>

- Mgaiwa, S. J. (2023). Predicting academics' job satisfaction from their perceived leadership styles: Evidence from Tanzania. *Cogent Psychology*, *11*(1), 1–22.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2022.2156839>
- Molines, M., Storme, M., & Mifsud, M. (2025). Promoting ethical voice in the police: a daily examination of ethical vision, LMX ambivalence, and interpersonal justice. *Public Management Review*, *27*(3), 679–701. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2023.2257213>
- Montañez-Juan, M. I., García-Buades, M. E., Sora-Miana, B., Ortiz-Bonnín, S., & Caballer-Hernández, A. (2019). Work design and job satisfaction: the moderating role of organizational justice. *Psychology: Organizations and Work Journal*, *19*(4), 853–858.
<https://doi.org/10.17652/rpot/2019.4.17510>
- Mushonga, S. M. (2023). Empowering supervisors: The moderation of supervisory justice in the relationship between organizational justice and work outcomes. *SAM Advanced Management Journal*, *88*(1), 48–60.
- National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research. (1979). *The Belmont report: Ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of human subjects of research*. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. <https://www.hhs.gov/ohrp/regulations-and-policy/belmont-report/read-the-belmont-report/index.html>
- Nunes, F. G., do Nascimento, G., & Martins, L. D. (2024). Do sectors (still) matter? Exploring similarities and differences between public, private, and non-profit organizations from an organizational identity perspective. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, *34*(4), 959–977. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21596>

- O'Connor, E. P., & Crowley-Henry, M. (2019). Exploring the relationship between exclusive talent management, perceived organizational justice and employee engagement: Bridging the literature. *Journal of Business Ethics*, *156*(4), 903–917.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-017-3543-1>
- Office of the New York State Attorney General. (2024). *Charities, nonprofits and fundraisers*.
<https://ag.ny.gov/resources/organizations/charities-nonprofits-fundraisers>
- Omar, A., Salessi, S., Vaamonde, J. D., & Urteaga, F. (2018). Psychometric properties of Colquitt's Organizational Justice Scale in Argentine workers. *Liberabit*, *24*(1), 61–79.
- Pan, X., Chen, M., Hao, Z., & Bi, W. (2018). The effects of organizational justice on positive organizational behavior: Evidence from a large-sample survey and a situational experiment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *8*(2315), 1–17.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.02315>
- Rahaman, H. M. S., Stouten, J., Decoster, S., & Camps, J. (2022). Antecedents of employee thriving at work: The roles of formalization, ethical leadership, and interpersonal justice. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, *71*(1), 3–26.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12308>
- Rahman, M. S. (2024). The interplay among distributive justice, procedural justice, self-efficacy, and career satisfaction: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Business Science and Applied Management*, *19*(1), 30–46. <https://doi.org/10.69864/ijbsam.19-1.181>
- Roch, S. G., Shannon, C. E., Martin, J. J., Swiderski, D., Agosta, J. P., & Shanock, L. R. (2019). Role of employee felt obligation and endorsement of the just world hypothesis: A social

- exchange theory investigation in an organizational justice context. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 49(4), 213–225. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jasp.12578>
- Roch, S. G., Zhuang, W., Park, J., Jin, F., & Brooks, R. R. (2024). Do just trainer behaviors matter? An investigation of felt obligation, affect, and endorsement of the just world hypothesis. *Journal of Personnel Psychology*, 23(2), 96–107. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1866-5888/a000334>
- Samosh, D., Maerz, A., Spitzmuller, M., & Boehm, S. (2023). Accommodation, interpersonal justice, and the turnover intentions of employees with disabilities. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 34(1), 128–153. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2021.1960582>
- Sarfraz, M., Qun, W., Abdullah, M. I., & Alvi, A. T. (2018). Employees' perception of corporate social responsibility impact on employee outcomes: Mediating role of organizational justice for small and medium enterprises (SMEs). *Sustainability*, 10(7), 2429–2450. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10072429>
- Sheeraz, M. I., Ahmad, U. N. U., Ishaq, M. I., & Nor, K. M. (2020). Moderating role of leader-member exchange between the relationship of organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce & Social Sciences*, 14(3), 735–760.
- Shehadeh, H. K. (2023). Organizational justice and its impact on job burnout (A case study in Zarqa Governmental Hospital). *Quality-Access to Success*, 24(194), 248–260. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/24.194.29>
- Silard, A. (2020). Interpersonal leader responses to secondary trauma in nonprofit human service organizations. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 30(4), 635–653. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21398>

- Singh, S. K., Varma, A., Budhwar, P. S., & Soral, P. (2024). Impact of supervisor's interactional justice and interpersonal affect on subordinates' performance rating: A signalling perspective. *British Journal of Management*, 35(3), 1296–1312.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8551.12758>
- Snipes, R. L., Pitts, J. P., Bryant, P. C., Huning, T. M., & Snipes, A. (2024). Job satisfaction and politics in the modern workplace: An empirical examination of the moderating effects of gender and age on the perception of organizational politics-job satisfaction relationship. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 36(3), 337–365.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10672-023-09449-2>
- Solomon, B. C., Nikolaev, B. N., & Shepherd, D. A. (2022). Does educational attainment promote job satisfaction? The bittersweet trade-offs between job resources, demands, and stress. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 107(7), 1227–1241.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0000904>
- Straatmann, T., Königshulte, S., Hatrup, K., & Hamborg, K.-C. (2020). Analysing mediating effects underlying the relationships between P–O fit, P–J fit, and organisational commitment. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 31(12), 1533–1559. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1416652>
- Strah, N., Rupp, D. E., Shao, R., King, E., & Skarlicki, D. (2024). Why have we not detected gender differences in organizational justice perceptions?! An evidenced-based argument for increasing inclusivity within justice research. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 45(7), 1117–1146. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2797>
- Suranata, G. A. E., Riana, I. G., Dewi, I. G. A. M., & Surya, I. B. K. (2025). Perceived organizational justice, organizational commitment, and employee performance in the

- public sector: Disclose the power of fairness. *Quality-Access to Success*, 26(207), 281–289. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/26.207.29>
- Tekingündüz, S., Karabel, E., Zekioğlu, A., & Sünbül, S. Ö. (2020). Modeling the relationship between organizational trust, job performance, identity and organizational identification. *Turkish Journal of Business Research*, 12(2), 1192–1206. <https://doi.org/10.20491/isarder.2020.905>
- Thomson, B., Rank, J., & Steidelmüller, C. (2021). The individual job impact of change and employees' well-being: Role clarity and interpersonal justice as leadership-related moderators. *Journal of Change Management*, 21(4), 391–411. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14697017.2021.1888771>
- United States Department of Health and Human Services (n.d.). *About HHS*. <https://www.hhs.gov/about/index.html>
- Vaamonde, J. D., Omar, A., & Salessi, S. (2018). From organizational justice perceptions to turnover intentions: The mediating effects of burnout and job satisfaction. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 14(3), 554–570. <https://doi.org/10.5964/ejop.v14i3.1490>
- van Dijke, M., De Cremer, D., Langendijk, G., & Anderson, C. (2018). Ranking low, feeling high: How hierarchical position and experienced power promote prosocial behavior in response to procedural justice. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 103(2), 164–181. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0000260>
- Vásquez-Trespalcios, E. M., Aranda-Beltrán, C., López-Palomar, M. D. R., Calderón-Mafud, J. L., Román-Calderón, J. P., Vaamonde, J. D., & Leon-Cortes, S. (2023). Organizational identification and burnout syndrome in healthcare workers: The mediating effect of organizational justice. *Work*, 75(3), 965–974. <https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-220107>

- Vincent, D., & Marmo, S. (2018). Commitment to social justice and its influence on job satisfaction and retention of nonprofit middle managers. *Human Service Organizations: Management, Leadership & Governance*, 42(5), 457–473.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23303131.2018.1532370>
- Weiss, D. J., Dawis, R. V., England, G. W., & Lofquist, L. H. (1999). Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire- selected items. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 4, 356-357.
- West, A. (2022). Employee turnover is impacting not-for-profits too: Competing for talent in the COVID-19 environment. *The CPA Journal*, 92(3/4), 46–47.
- Wikhamn, W., Asplund, K., & Dries, N. (2021). Identification with management and the organisation as key mechanisms in explaining employee reactions to talent status. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 31(4), 956–976. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12335>
- Xu, X., Cropanzano, R., McWha-Hermann, I., & Lu, C. (2024). Multiple salary comparisons, distributive justice, and employee withdrawal. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 109(10), 1533–1554. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001184>
- Yuan, G., Jia, L., & Zhao, J. (2016). Organizational identification moderates the impact of organizational justice on job satisfaction. *Work*, 54(1), 189–195.
<https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-162271>
- Zagenczyk, T. J., Purvis, R. L., Cruz, K. S., Thoroughgood, C. N., & Sawyer, K. B. (2021). Context and social exchange: perceived ethical climate strengthens the relationships between perceived organizational support and organizational identification and commitment. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 32(22), 4752–4771. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2019.1706618>

- Zagenczyk, T. J., & Powell, E. E. (2023). Social networks and citizenship behavior: The mediating effect of organizational identification. *Human Resource Management, 62*(4), 461–475. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.22144>
- Zhao, R., & Zhang, C. (2024). Racial pay disparity of social workers in nonprofit, for-profit, and government human services organizations. *Human Service Organizations: Management, Leadership & Governance, 48*(4), 455–473. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23303131.2023.2227231>
- Zhao, R., Bies, A., & Kim, S. M. (2025). Employee compensation of nonprofit child welfare agencies in New York: Crises and strategies. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership, 35*(4), 559–570. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21629>